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2 This word version is the penultimate version of the manuscript.

3 The final version is published in eLife

4 <https://elifesciences.org/articles/84658>'.

5 The earlier bioRxiv version is substantially different.

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8 A framework for community curation of 9 interspecies interactions literature

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20 Abstract

21 The quantity and complexity of data being generated and published in biology has increased substantially,
22 but few methods exist for capturing knowledge about phenotypes derived from molecular interactions
23 between diverse groups of species, in such a way that is amenable to data-driven biology and research. To
24 improve access to this knowledge, we have constructed a framework for the curation of the scientific
25 literature studying interspecies interactions, using data curated for the Pathogen–Host Interactions
26 Database (PHI-base) as a case study. The framework provides a curation tool, phenotype ontology and
27 controlled vocabularies to curate pathogen–host interaction data, at the level of the host, pathogen, strain,
28 gene and genotype. The concept of a multispecies genotype, the ‘metagenotype’, is introduced to facilitate
29 capturing changes in the disease-causing abilities of pathogens, and host resistance or susceptibility
30 observed by gene alterations. We report on this framework and describe PHI-Canto, a community curation
31 tool for use by publication authors.

32 Introduction

33 Recent technological advancements across the biological sciences have resulted in an increasing volume
34 of peer-reviewed publications reporting experimental data and conclusions. To increase the value of this
35 highly fragmented knowledge, biocurators manually extract the data from publications and represent it in a
36 standardized and interconnected way following the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and
37 Reusable) Data Principles (International Society for Biocuration, 2018; Wilkinson et al., 2016). Curated
38 functional data is then made available in online databases, either organism- or clade-specific (e.g., model
39 organism databases) or those supporting multiple kingdoms of life (e.g., PHI-base (Urban et al., 2022),
40 Alliance of Genomes Resources (Alliance of Genome Resources Consortium, 2020) or UniProt (UniProt
41 Consortium, 2021)). Due to the complexity of the biology and the specificity of the curation requirements,
42 manual biocuration is currently the most reliable way to capture information about function and phenotype
43 in databases and knowledge bases (Wood, Sternberg, & Lipshitz, 2022). For pathogen–host interactions,
44 the original publications do not provide details of specific strains, variants, and their associated genotypes
45 and phenotypes, nor the relative impact on pathogenicity and virulence, in a standardized machine-
46 readable format. The expert curator synergizes knowledge from different representations (text, graphs,
47 images) into clearly defined machine-readable syntax. The development of curation tools with clear

48 workflows supporting the use of biological ontologies and controlled vocabularies has standardized curation
49 efforts, reduced ambiguity in annotation and improved the maintenance of the curated corpus as biological
50 knowledge evolves (International Society for Biocuration, 2018).

51 The pathogen–host interaction research communities are an example of a domain of the biological
52 sciences exhibiting a literature deluge (Figure 1). The Pathogen–Host Interactions Database, PHI-base
53 (phi-base.org), is an open-access FAIR biological database containing data on bacterial, fungal and protist
54 genes proven to affect (or not to affect) the outcome of pathogen–host interactions (Rodriguez-Iglesias et
55 al., 2016; Urban et al., 2020; Urban et al., 2022). Since 2005, PHI-base has manually curated phenotype
56 data associated with underlying genome-level changes from peer-reviewed pathogen–host interaction
57 literature. Information is also provided on the target sites of some anti-infective chemistries (Urban et al.,
58 2020). Knowledge related to pathogen–host interaction phenotypes is increasingly relevant, as infectious
59 microbes continually threaten global food security, human health across the life course, farmed animal
60 health and wellbeing, tree health and ecosystem resilience (Brown et al., 2012; Fisher, Hawkins, Sanglard,
61 & Gurr, 2018; Fisher et al., 2012; Fisher et al., 2022; Smith, Machalaba, Seifman, Feferholtz, & Karesh,
62 2019). Rising resistance to antimicrobial compounds, increased globalization and climate change indicate
63 that infectious microbes will present ever greater economic and societal threats (Bebber, Ramotowski, &
64 Gurr, 2013; Chaloner, Gurr, & Bebber, 2021; Cook et al., 2021). In order to curate relevant publications into
65 PHI-base (version 4), professional curators have, since 2011, entered 81 different data types into a text file
66 (Urban et al., 2017). However, increasing publication numbers and data complexity required more robust
67 curation procedures and greater involvement from publication authors.

68 We were unable to locate any curation frameworks or tools capable of capturing the interspecies
69 interactions required for PHI-base. PomBase, the fission yeast (*Schizosaccharomyces pombe*) database
70 developed Canto, a web-based tool supporting curation by both professional biocurators and publication
71 authors (Rutherford, Harris, Lock, Oliver, & Wood, 2014). Canto already had support for annotating genes
72 from multiple species in the same curation session, but it could not support annotation of the interactions
73 between species, nor the annotation of genes from naturally occurring strains. We extended and
74 customized Canto to support the annotation of multiple strains of multiple species, and the modeling and
75 annotation of interspecies interactions between pathogens and hosts, to create a new tool: PHI-Canto (the
76 Pathogen–Host Interaction Community Annotation Tool). Likewise, there were no existing biomedical
77 ontologies that could accurately describe pathogen–host interaction phenotypes at the depth and breadth

78 required for PHI-base. Infectious disease formation depends on a series of complex and dynamic
79 interactions between pathogenic species and their potential hosts, and also requires the correct biotic
80 and/or abiotic environmental conditions (Scholthof, 2007), as illustrated by the concept of the ‘disease
81 triangle’ (Figure 2). All these interrelated factors must be recorded in order to sufficiently describe a
82 pathogen–host interaction.

83 In this study, three key issues were addressed in order to develop the curation framework for interspecies
84 interactions: firstly, to support the classification of genes as ‘pathogen’ or ‘host’, and enable the variations
85 of the same gene in different strains to be captured; secondly, formulating the concept of a ‘metagenotype’
86 to represent the interaction between specific strains of both a pathogen and a host within a multispecies
87 genotype; and thirdly, developing supporting ontologies and controlled vocabularies, including the generic
88 Pathogen–Host Interaction Phenotype Ontology (PHIPO), to annotate phenotypes connected to genotypes
89 at the level of a single species (pathogen or host) and multiple species (pathogen–host interaction
90 phenotypes). Leading on from these advances, we discuss how the overall curation framework described
91 herein, the concept of annotating metagenotypes, and ongoing generic ontology development, is a suitable
92 approach for adoption and use by a wide range of research communities in the life sciences focused on
93 different types of interspecies interactions occurring within or across kingdoms in different environments
94 and at multiple (micro to macro) scales.

96 Results

97 Enabling multispecies curation with UniProtKB accessions

98 In any curation context, stable identifiers are required for annotated entities. The UniProt Knowledgebase
99 (UniProtKB) (UniProt Consortium, 2021) is universally recognized, provides broad taxonomic protein
100 coverage, and manually curates standard nomenclature across protein families. Protein sequences are
101 both manually and computationally annotated in UniProtKB, providing a wealth of data on catalytic
102 activities, protein structures and protein–protein interactions, Gene Ontology (GO) annotations and links to
103 PHI-base phenotypes (Ashburner et al., 2000; Gene Ontology Consortium, 2021; Urban et al., 2022). To
104 improve interoperability with other resources, we used UniProtKB accession numbers for retrieving protein

105 entities, gene names and species information for display in PHI-Canto. PHI-Canto accesses the UniProtKB
106 API to automatically retrieve the entities and their associated data.

107 Developing the metagenotype to capture interspecies interactions

108 To enable annotation of interspecies interactions, we developed the concept of a ‘metagenotype’, that
109 represents the combination of a pathogen genotype and a host genotype (Figure 3). A metagenotype is
110 created after the individual genotypes from both species are created. Each metagenotype can be
111 annotated with pathogen–host interaction phenotypes to capture changes in pathogenicity (caused by
112 alterations to the pathogen) and changes in virulence (caused by alterations to the host and/or the
113 pathogen). Pathogenicity is a property of the pathogen that describes the ability of the pathogen to cause
114 an infectious disease in another organism. When a pathogenic organism causes disease, the severity of
115 the disease that occurs is referred to as ‘virulence’ and this can also be dependent upon the host organism.
116 Metagenotypes must always include at least one named pathogen gene with a genotype of interest, but
117 need not include a host gene if none is referenced in a given experiment: instead, the wild-type host
118 species and strain may be used for the host part of the metagenotype.

119 Annotation types and annotation extensions in PHI-Canto

120 In PHI-Canto, ‘annotation’ is the task of relating a specific piece of knowledge to a biological feature. Three
121 types of biological features can be annotated in PHI-Canto: genes, genotypes and metagenotypes.
122 Genotypes can be further specified as pathogen genotypes or host genotypes. Each of these biological
123 features has a corresponding set of annotation types. The relation between biological features, annotation
124 types and the values that can be used for annotation are shown in Table 1. To capture additional
125 biologically relevant information associated with an annotation, curators use the concept of annotation
126 extensions (which include Gene Ontology annotations described by Huntley et al., 2014) to extend the
127 primary annotation. For Canto and PHI-Canto, the meaning of ‘annotation extension’ was broadened to
128 capture additional properties related to the annotation, such as the metagenotype used as an experimental
129 control. The aforementioned additional properties are simply referred to as ‘annotation extensions’ (AEs) in
130 this study (Table 1, Supplementary file 1 and Supplementary file 2). Descriptions of the new AEs for PHI-
131 Canto and the core collection of AEs from Canto are available in the PHI-Canto user documentation (see
132 the Code availability section).

133 Metagenotypes can be annotated with terms from an ontology or controlled vocabulary following either the
134 'pathogen–host interaction phenotype', 'gene-for-gene phenotype' or 'disease name' annotation types
135 (Table 1). Phenotype annotations on metagenotypes can be supported by AEs providing additional
136 qualifying information required to fully interpret the experiment, such as the infected tissue of the host.

137 Phenotypes can also be curated for single species experiments involving either the pathogen or host,
138 following the 'single species phenotype' annotation workflow (Table 1). Single species phenotype
139 annotations have a selection of AEs available, including the protein assayed in the experiment and the
140 severity of the observed phenotype (see example from PMID:22314539 in Appendix 1).

141 PHI-Canto also supports the annotation of gene and gene product attributes to represent the evolved
142 functional role of a gene product, described here as the 'gene annotation' workflow (Table 1). The Gene
143 Ontology is used for annotation of a gene product's molecular functions, biological processes and cellular
144 components, while PSI-MOD is used for the annotation of protein modifications (Montecchi-Palazzi et al.,
145 2008), and BioGRID experiment types are used to capture genetic and physical interactions (Oughtred et
146 al., 2021). GO annotations are submitted to the EBI GO Annotation Database (GOA), from where they are
147 propagated to the main GO knowledge base (Gene Ontology Consortium, 2021; Huntley et al., 2015).

148 Trial curation of interspecies interaction publications

149 Ten publications covering a wide range of typical plant, human, and animal pathogen–host interactions
150 were selected for trial curation in PHI-Canto before the tool was made available to publication authors and
151 communities to add further publications (Table 2). These publications included experiments with early
152 acting pathogen virulence proteins, the first host targets of pathogen effectors, and resistance to antifungal
153 chemistries. These publications guided the development of the ontology terms and controlled vocabulary
154 terms that were required for PHI-Canto, as well as the curation methods required for different experiments.
155 Major curation problems and their solutions are summarized in Table 3, and example annotations are
156 described below and in Appendix 1 and Appendix 2.

157 Curating an experiment with a metagenotype

158 A large proportion of the curation in PHI-Canto requires the use of metagenotypes: one of the simpler
159 cases involves early-acting virulence proteins, where a genetically modified pathogen is inoculated onto a

160 host (without a host gene being specified). A metagenotype is created to connect the genotypes of both
161 species and is annotated with a phenotype term. These experiments are curated following the ‘pathogen–
162 host interaction phenotype’ workflow, including any relevant AEs (Table 1). This two-step curation process
163 is illustrated by PMID:29020037 curation (Table 2, Appendix 1 and Appendix 2) where the GT2 gene is
164 deleted from the fungal plant pathogen *Zymoseptoria tritici* and inoculated onto wheat plants; the observed
165 phenotype ‘absence of pathogen-associated host lesions’ (PHIPO:0000481) is annotated to the
166 metagenotype; and the AE for ‘infective ability’ is annotated with ‘loss of pathogenicity’ compared to the
167 unaltered pathogen.

168 Curating pathogen effector experiments

169 A pathogen effector is defined as an entity transferred between the pathogen and the host that is known or
170 suspected to be responsible for either activating or suppressing a host process commonly involved in
171 defense (Houterman et al., 2009; Jones & Dangl, 2006) (Figure 2). To curate an effector experiment, a
172 metagenotype is created and annotated with a phenotype term. To indicate that the pathogen gene
173 functions as an effector, it is necessary to make a concurrent gene annotation (Table 1) with the GO
174 biological process term ‘effector-mediated modulation of host process’ (GO:0140418) or an appropriate
175 descendant term. This GO term (GO:0140418) and its descendant terms were created in collaboration with
176 the Gene Ontology Consortium (GOC) and are used for pathogen effectors in PHI-base (version 5)
177 (Supplementary file 3). Reported activities of pathogen effectors can also be curated with GO molecular
178 function terms. An example of curation of a pathogen effector experiment is illustrated using
179 PMID:31804478 (Table 2 and Appendix 1) where the pathogen effector Pst_12806 from *Puccinia striiformis*
180 suppresses pattern-triggered immunity in a tobacco leaf model. Here, the metagenotype is annotated with
181 the phenotype ‘decreased level of host defense-induced callose deposition’ (PHIPO:0001015) and the
182 effector is annotated with ‘effector-mediated suppression of host pattern-triggered immunity’ (GO:0052034).
183 A further experiment demonstrated that the pathogen effector protein was able to bind to the natural host
184 (wheat) protein PetC and inhibit its enzyme activity, resulting in a GO molecular function annotation
185 ‘enzyme inhibitor activity’ (GO:0004857) for Pst_12806, with PetC captured as the target protein (see
186 Appendix 1).

187 Curating experiments with a gene-for-gene relationship

188 For a gene-for-gene pathogen–host interaction type, the ‘gene-for-gene phenotype’ metagenotype workflow
189 is followed (a gene-for-gene interaction is when a known genetic interaction is conferred by a specific
190 pathogen avirulence gene product and its cognate host resistance gene product) (Figure 2c, d, further
191 described in the figure legend) (Flor, 1956; Jones & Dangl, 2006; Kanyuka, Igna, Solomon, & Oliver,
192 2022)). The metagenotypes and phenotype annotations are made in the same way as the standard
193 ‘pathogen–host interaction phenotype’ workflow, but with different supporting data. A new AE was created
194 to indicate the following three components of the interaction: i) the compatibility of the interaction, ii) the
195 functional status of the pathogen gene, and iii) the functional status of the host gene. An example of an
196 annotation for a biotrophic pathogen gene-for-gene interaction has been illustrated with PMID:20601497
197 (Table 2 and Appendix 1). Inverse gene-for-gene relationships occur with necrotrophic pathogens, where
198 the pathogen necrotrophic effector interacts with a gene product from the corresponding host susceptibility
199 locus and activates a host response that benefits the pathogen (a compatible interaction). If the
200 necrotrophic effector cannot interact with the host target, then no disease occurs (an incompatible
201 interaction) (Breen, Williams, Winterberg, Kobe, & Solomon, 2016). An example of an inverse gene-for-
202 gene interaction using the appropriate AEs is illustrated with PMID:22241993 (Table 2 and Appendix 1).

203 Curating an experiment with a single species genotype in the presence or absence 204 of a chemical

205 Single species genotypes (pathogen or host) can also be annotated with phenotypes following the ‘single
206 species phenotype’ workflow (Table 1). This is illustrated using PMID:22314539 in Table 2 (and Appendix
207 1) with an example of an *in vitro* pathogen chemistry phenotype, where a single nucleotide mutation in the
208 *Aspergillus flavus* CYP51c gene confers ‘resistance to voriconazole’ (PHIPO:0000590), an antifungal
209 agent.

210 Supporting curation of legacy information

211 PHI-Canto’s curation workflows maintain support for nine high-level terms that describe phenotypic
212 outcomes essential for taxonomically diverse interspecies comparisons, which were the primary annotation
213 method used in previous versions of PHI-base (Urban et al., 2015) and which are displayed in the Ensembl
214 Genomes browser (Yates et al., 2022). For example, the ‘infective ability’ AE can be used to annotate the

215 following subset of high-level terms: 'loss of pathogenicity', 'unaffected pathogenicity', 'reduced virulence',
216 'increased virulence' and 'loss of mutualism' (formerly 'enhanced antagonism'). The mapping between the
217 nine high-level terms and the PHI-Canto curation process is further described in Supplementary file 3.

218 Resolving additional problems with curating complex pathogen–host interactions

219 Table 3 shows a selection of the problems encountered during the development of PHI-Canto and the
220 solutions we identified: for example, recording the delivery mechanism used within the pathogen–host
221 interaction experiment. New experimental condition terms were developed with a prefix of 'delivery
222 mechanism': for example, 'delivery mechanism: agrobacterium', 'delivery mechanism: heterologous
223 organism', and 'delivery mechanism: pathogen inoculation'. Another issue encountered was how to record
224 a physical interaction between two proteins from different species, especially for the curation of pathogen
225 effectors and their discovered first host targets. This was resolved by adapting the existing Canto module
226 for curating physical interactions to support two different species.

227 Development of the Pathogen–Host Interaction Phenotype Ontology and 228 additional data lists

229 To support the annotation of phenotypes in PHI-Canto, the Pathogen–Host Interaction Phenotype Ontology
230 (PHIPO) was developed. PHIPO is a species-neutral phenotype ontology that describes a broad range of
231 pathogen–host interaction phenotypes. Terms in PHIPO were developed following a pre-compositional
232 approach, where the term names and semantics were composed from existing terms from other ontologies,
233 in order to make the curation process easier. For example, the curator annotates 'resistance to penicillin'
234 (PHIPO:0000692) instead of 'increased resistance to chemical' (PHIPO:0000022) and 'penicillin'
235 (CHEBI:17334) separately. Terms in PHIPO have logical definitions that follow design patterns from the
236 uPheno ontology (Shefchek et al., 2020), and mapping PHIPO terms to uPheno patterns is an ongoing
237 effort. These logical definitions provide relations between phenotypes in PHIPO and terms in other
238 ontologies, such as PATO, GO, and ChEBI. PHIPO is available in OWL and OBO formats from the OBO
239 Foundry (Jackson et al., 2021).

240 PHI-Canto uses additional controlled vocabularies derived from data in PHI-base. To enable PHI-Canto to
241 distinguish between pathogen and host organisms, we extracted a list of > 250 pathogen and > 200 host

242 species from PHI-base (Supplementary file 4). A curated list of strain names and their synonyms for the
243 species currently curated in PHI-base was also developed for use in PHI-Canto (Supplementary file 4 and
244 5). PHI-base uses 'strain' as a grouping term for natural pathogen isolates, host cultivars and landraces, all
245 of which are included in the curated list. The curation of pathogen strain designations was motivated by the
246 NCBI Taxonomy's decision to discontinue the assignment of strain-level taxonomic identifiers (Federhen et
247 al., 2014) and a lack of standardized nomenclature for natural isolates of non-model species. New strain
248 designations can be requested by curators and are reviewed by an expert prior to inclusion to ensure that
249 each describes a novel strain designation rather than a new synonym for an existing strain.

250 Annotations in PHI-Canto include experimental evidence, which is specified by a term from a subset of the
251 Evidence & Conclusion Ontology (ECO) (Giglio et al., 2019). Experimental evidence codes specific to
252 pathogen–host interaction experiments have been developed and submitted to ECO. Phenotype
253 annotations also include experimental conditions that are relevant to the experiment being curated, which
254 are sourced from the PHI-base Experimental Conditions Ontology (PHI-ECO).

255 PHI-Canto includes a 'disease name' annotation type (Table 1) for annotating the name of the disease
256 caused by an interaction between the pathogen and host specified in a wild type metagenotype (this
257 annotation type is described in the PHI-Canto user documentation and in Appendix 2). Diseases are
258 specified by a controlled vocabulary of disease names (called PHIDO), which was derived from disease
259 names curated in previous versions of PHI-base (Urban et al., 2022). PHIDO was developed as a
260 placeholder to allow disease names to be annotated on a wide variety of pathogen interactions, including
261 those on plant, human, animal and invertebrate hosts, especially where such diseases were not described
262 in any existing ontology.

263 Summary of the PHI-Canto curation process

264 The PHI-Canto curation process is outlined in Figure 4, Figure 4 – figure supplement 1, the PHI-Canto user
265 documentation, a detailed worked example provided in Appendix 2 and curation tutorials on the PHI-base
266 YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@PHI-base>), under the playlist 'PHI-Canto tutorial videos'.
267 Each curation session is associated with one publication (using its PubMed identifier). One or more
268 curators can collaborate on curating the same publication. An instructional email is sent by PHI-Canto to
269 curators when they begin a new curation session, and PHI-base provides further guidelines on what

270 information is needed to curate a publication in PHI-Canto (Figure 4 – figure supplement 2) and how to
271 identify UniProtKB accession numbers from reference proteomes (Figure 4 – figure supplement 3).

272 The curator first adds genes from the publication, then creates alleles from genes, genotypes from alleles,
273 and metagenotypes from pathogen and host genotypes. Pathogen genotypes and host genotypes are
274 created on separate pages, that only include genes from the relevant pathogen or host. A genotype can
275 consist of multiple alleles, therefore a metagenotype can contain multiple alleles from both the pathogen
276 and the host. A 'copy and edit' feature allows the creation of multiple similar annotations.

277 To make annotations, the curator selects a gene, genotype, or metagenotype to annotate, then selects a
278 term from a controlled vocabulary, adds experimental evidence, experimental conditions, AEs (where
279 available), and any additional comments. The curator can also specify a figure or table number from the
280 original publication as part of the annotation. Curators can use a term suggestion feature to suggest new
281 terms for any controlled vocabulary used by PHI-Canto, and experimental conditions can be entered as
282 free text if no suitable condition is found in PHI-ECO. Subsequently, new condition suggestions are
283 reviewed and approved by expert curators. The curation session can be saved and paused at various
284 stages during the curation process. Once the curation process is complete, the curator submits the session
285 for review by a nominated species expert.

286 Display and interoperability of data

287 The process of incorporating FAIR principles fully into the PHI-base curation process will promote
288 interoperability between data resources (Wilkinson et al., 2016). Figure 5 illustrates the internal and
289 external resource dependencies for curation in PHI-Canto. URLs and descriptions of the use of each
290 resource are provided in Figure 5 – figure supplement 1. All data curated in PHI-Canto will be displayed in
291 the new gene-centric version 5 of PHI-base, introduced in Urban et al., 2022. Additional detail on the data
292 types displayed in PHI-base 5 is available in Table 4. Reciprocally, components of the interspecies curation
293 framework (Figure 6a) will provide data to other resources (Figure 6b). For example, GO terms will be used
294 in curation with PHI-Canto and these annotations will be made available in the GO knowledge base via
295 submission to the GOA Database (Gene Ontology Consortium, 2021; Huntley et al., 2015). PHI-base is a
296 member of ELIXIR, an organization that aims to unite leading life science resources and a major proponent
297 of FAIR data (Durinx et al., 2016).

Discussion

Scalable and accurate curation of data within the scientific literature is of paramount importance due to the increasing quantity of publications and the complexity of experiments within each publication. PHI-base is an example of a freely available, manually curated database, which has been curating literature using professional curators since 2005 (Winnenburg et al., 2006).

Here, we have described the development of PHI-Canto to allow the curation of the interspecies pathogen–host interaction literature by professional curators and publication authors. This curated data is then made available on the new gene-centric version 5 of PHI-base, where all information (i.e. new and existing) on a single gene from several publications is presented on a single page, with links to external resources providing information on interacting genes, proteins and other entities.

Several adaptations to the original single-species community annotation tool, Canto (Rutherford et al., 2014), were required to convert this tool for interspecies use. Notably, the need to annotate an interaction involving two different organisms necessitated the development of a novel concept, the ‘metagenotype’ (Figure 3), in order to record a combined experimental genotype involving both a pathogen and a host. This is, to our knowledge, the first example of such an approach to interspecies interaction curation.

Curation of pathogen–host interactions in PHI-Canto also necessitated the development of a new phenotype ontology (PHIPO) to annotate pathogen–host interaction phenotypes in sufficient detail across the broad range of host species that were curated in PHI-base ($n = 234$ in version 4.14 of PHI-base). The functional annotation of genes involved in interspecies interactions is a complex and challenging task, requiring ongoing modifications to the Gene Ontology and occasional major refactoring to deprecate legacy terms (Gene Ontology Consortium, 2021). PHIPO development and maintenance will also be an ongoing task, with both authors and professional curators requesting new terms and edits to existing terms and the ontology structure. Maintenance will be made more sustainable by the incorporation of logical definitions that are aligned across phenotype ontologies in collaboration with the uPheno project (Shefchek et al., 2020).

To improve the efficiency of the curation process, we are suggesting that authors follow an author checklist during manuscript preparation (Appendix 3). This will improve the presentation of key information (e.g.,

325 species names, gene identifiers etc.) in published manuscripts, thus enabling more efficient and
326 comprehensive curation that is human- and machine-readable. The annotation procedures described here
327 using PHI-Canto can be used to extract data buried in small-scale publications and increase the
328 accessibility of the curated article to a wider range of potential users, for example computational biologists,
329 thereby improving the FAIR status of the data. The current data in PHI-base has been obtained from > 200
330 journals (Figure 7) and therefore represents highly fragmented knowledge which is exceptionally difficult to
331 use by professionals in other disciplines. The feasibility of scalable community curation with Canto is
332 evidenced by PomBase (Lock et al., 2020), where Canto *S. pombe* annotations from over 1000
333 publications are provided by publication authors, with the data made available within 24 hours of review
334 (<https://curation.pombase.org/pombe/stats/annotation>).

335 With regards to our focus on manual curation, we recognize that great progress has been made with
336 machine learning (ML) approaches in recent times. However, Wood, Sternberg & Lipshitz (2022) note that
337 the data being curated from publications are “categorical, highly complex, and with hundreds of thousands
338 of heterogeneous classes, often not explicitly labeled”. There are no published examples of ML approaches
339 outperforming an expert curator in accuracy, which is paramount in the medical field. However, curation by
340 experts could provide a highly reliable corpus that could be used for training ML systems. Our aspiration is
341 that ML and expert curators can collaborate in a virtuous cycle whereby expert curators continually review
342 and refine the ML models, while the manual work of finding publications and entity recognition is handled
343 by the ML system.

344 Our future intentions are two-fold: firstly, a graph-based representation of the data will be enabled by
345 integration with knowledge network generation tools, such as Knetminer (Hassani-Pak et al., 2021), where
346 subgraphs of the knowledge graph could be embedded into each gene-centric page on the PHI-base 5
347 website. Secondly, within PHI-Canto, we intend to address the issues associated with maximizing the
348 inherent value of the natural sequence variation between species strains, and the associated altered
349 phenotypic outcomes observed at multiple scales, in different types of interactions and/or environments.
350 PHI-base already contains information on numerous species with multiple experimental strains, and natural
351 sequence variation between strains can result in alterations at the genome level that affect the
352 subsequently observed phenotypes. Strain-specific sequence variation is not captured in the reference
353 proteomes stored by UniProt, even though accession numbers from these proteomes are often used in

354 PHI-Canto. Currently, when a curator enters a gene with a taxonomic identifier below the species rank,
355 PHI-Canto maps the identifier to the corresponding identifier at the species rank (thus removing any strain
356 details from the organism name), and the curator specifies a strain to differentiate gene variants in naturally
357 occurring strains. However, this does not change the taxonomic identifier linked to the UniProtKB accession
358 number (nor its sequence), so the potential for inaccuracy remains. To mitigate this, the future plan is to
359 record the strain-specific sequence of the gene using an accession number from a database from the
360 International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (Arita, Karsch-Mizrachi, & Cochrane, 2021).

361 The release of PHI-Canto to the community will occur gradually through various routes. Community
362 curation will be promoted by working with journals to capture the publication data at source, at the point of
363 manuscript acceptance. We will also target specific research communities (e.g., those working on a
364 particular pathogen and/or research topic) by inviting authors to curate their own publications. Authors may
365 contact us directly to request support while curating their publications in PHI-Canto.

366 PHI-Canto, PHI-base and PHIPO were devised and built over the past seven years to serve the research
367 needs of a specific international research community interested in exploring the wide diversity of common
368 and species-specific mechanisms underlying pathogen attack and host defense in plant, animals, humans
369 and other host organisms caused by fungi, protists and bacteria. However, it should be noted that the
370 underlying developments to Canto's data model – especially the concept of annotating metagenotypes –
371 could be of use to communities focused on different types of interspecies interactions. Possible future uses
372 of the PHI-Canto schema could include insect–plant interactions (both beneficial and detrimental),
373 endosymbiotic relationships such as mycorrhiza–plant rhizosphere interactions, nodulating bacteria–plant
374 rhizosphere interactions, fungi–fungi interactions, plant–plant interactions or bacteria–insect interactions,
375 and non-pathogenic relationships in natural environments such as bulk soil, rhizosphere, phyllosphere, air,
376 freshwater, estuarine water or seawater, and human–animal, animal–bird, human–insect, animal–insect,
377 bird–insect interactions in various anatomical locations (e.g. gut, lung, and skin). The schema could also be
378 extended to situations where phenotype–genotype relations have been established for predator–prey
379 relationships or where there is competition in herbivore–herbivore, predator–predator or prey–prey
380 relationships in the air, on land or in the water. Finally, the schema could be used to explore strain to strain
381 interactions within a species when different biological properties have been noted. Customizing Canto to
382 use other ontologies and controlled vocabularies is as simple as editing a configuration file, as shown in
383 Source code 1.

384

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Methods

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Changes to the Canto data model and configuration

387

PHI-Canto stores its data in a series of relational databases using the SQLite database engine. A primary

388

database stores data shared across all curation sessions, and each curation session also has its own

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database to store data related to a single publication (such as genes, genotypes, metagenotypes, etc.).

390

PHI-Canto can export its data as a JSON file or more specialized formats, for example the GO Annotation

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File (GAF) format.

392

To implement PHI-Canto several new entities were added to the Canto data model in order to support

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pathogen–host curation, as well as new configuration options (the new entities are illustrated in Figure 3 –

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figure supplement 1). These entities were ‘strain’, ‘metagenotype’ and ‘metagenotype annotation’. The

395

complete data model for PHI-Canto is illustrated in Figure 3 – figure supplements 2 and 3.

396

Pathogen and host roles

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Genotype entities in PHI-Canto’s data model were extended with an attribute indicating their status as a

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pathogen genotype or a host genotype. Genotypes inherit their status (as pathogen or host) from the

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organism, which in turn is classified as a pathogen or host based on a configuration file that contains the

400

NCBI Taxonomy ID (taxid) (Schoch et al., 2020) of each host species in PHI-base. Only host taxids need to

401

be specified since PHI-Canto defaults to classifying a species as a pathogen if its taxid is not found in the

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configuration file.

403

PHI-Canto also loads lists of pathogen and host species that specify the scientific name, taxid, and

404

common name (if any) of each species. These species lists are used to specify which host species can be

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added as a component of the metagenotype in the absence of a specific studied gene, and to override the

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scientific name provided by UniProtKB in favor of the name used by a scientific community studying the

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species (for example, to control whether the anamorph or teleomorph name of a fungal species is displayed

408

in PHI-Canto’s user interface).

409 Metagenotype implementation

410 Metagenotypes were implemented by adding a 'metagenotype' entity to PHI-Canto's data model. The
411 metagenotype is the composition of two genotype entities. We also changed the data model to allow
412 annotations to be related to metagenotypes (previously, only genes and genotypes could be related to
413 annotations).

414 Strain implementation

415 Support for strain curation was implemented by adding a 'strain' entity to PHI-Canto's data model. Strains
416 are related to an organism entity and its related genotype entities. In the user interface, PHI-Canto uses the
417 taxid of the organism to filter an autocomplete system, such that only the strains of the specified organism
418 are suggested. The autocomplete system can also use synonyms in the strain list to suggest a strain based
419 on its synonymous names. Unknown strains are represented by a preset value of 'Unknown strain'.

420 Ontologies

421 PHIPO was developed using the Protégé ontology editor (Musen & Protégé Team, 2015). PHIPO uses
422 OBO namespaces to allow PHI-Canto to filter the terms in the ontology by annotation type, ensuring that
423 genotypes are annotated with single-species phenotypes and metagenotypes with pathogen–host
424 interaction phenotypes.

425 PHI-ECO was also developed using Protégé, starting from a list of experimental conditions originally
426 developed by PomBase. PHIDO was initially derived from a list of diseases already curated in PHI-base
427 and is now maintained as a flat file that is converted into an OBO file using ROBOT (Jackson et al., 2019).

428 Data availability

429 Pathogen–Host Interaction Phenotype Ontology: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/phi-po.owl>

430 PHI-base Experimental Conditions Ontology: <https://github.com/PHI-base/phi-eco>

431 PHIDO, the controlled vocabulary of disease names: <https://github.com/PHI-base/phido>

432 PHIPO Extension Ontology for gene-for-gene phenotypes: https://github.com/PHI-base/phi-po_ext

433 Location of species and strain lists used by PHI-Canto: <https://github.com/PHI-base/data>

434 PHI-Canto approved curation sessions (December 2022): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7428788>

435 Code availability

436 PHI-Canto's source code is available on GitHub, at <https://github.com/PHI-base/canto>. PHI-Canto is freely
437 licensed under the GNU General Public License version 3, with no restrictions on copying, distributing, or
438 modifying the code, for commercial use or otherwise, provided any derivative works are licensed under the
439 same terms. PHI-base provides an online demo version of PHI-Canto at <https://demo-canto.phi-base.org/>
440 which can be used for evaluating the tool. The demo version and the main version of PHI-Canto will remain
441 freely available online.

442 Canto's source code is available on GitHub, at <https://github.com/pombase/canto>. Canto is also freely
443 licensed under the GNU General Public License version 3.

444 The source code for PHI-Canto's user documentation is available on GitHub, at [https://github.com/PHI-](https://github.com/PHI-base/canto-docs)
445 [base/canto-docs](https://github.com/PHI-base/canto-docs). The user documentation is licensed under the MIT license. The published format of the
446 user documentation is available online at <https://canto.phi-base.org/docs/index>.

447 The source code for PHIPO is available on GitHub under a Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 license,
448 at <https://github.com/PHI-base/phiipo>.

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592 Ethics declarations

593 Competing interests

594 The authors declare no competing interests.

Tables and Figures

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Figure 1. Increase of molecular host-pathogen interaction publications and gene phenotype information during the last 35 years curated in PHI-base. Grey bars show the number of publications in the Web of Science Core Collection database retrieved with search term “(fung* or yeast) and (gene or factor) and (pathogenicity or virulen* or avirulence gene*)”. Black vertical bars show the number of articles retrieved from PubMed (searching on title and abstract). Black and white triangles show the number of curated animal and plant pathogen genes, respectively.

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 608 **Figure 2.** Schematic representation of pathogen–host interactions. (a) the disease triangle illustrates the
 609 requirement for the correct abiotic and biotic environmental conditions to ensure disease when an adapted
 610 pathogen encounters a suitable host; (b) a non gene-for-gene genetic relationship where compatible
 611 interactions result in disease on all host genotypes (depicted as genotypes 1–4), but the extent of disease
 612 formation is influenced to a greater or lesser extent by the presence or absence of a single pathogen
 613 virulence gene product X. In host genotypes 1 and 3, the pathogen gene product X is the least required for
 614 disease formation. The size of each black oval in each of the eight genetic interactions indicates the
 615 severity of the disease phenotype observed, with a larger oval indicating greater severity: (c) a gene-for-
 616 gene genetic relationship. In this genetic system, considerable specificity is observed, which is based on
 617 the direct or indirect interaction of a pathogen avirulence (*Avr*) effector gene product with a host resistance
 618 (*R*) gene product to determine specific recognition (an incompatible interaction), which is typically observed
 619 in biotrophic interactions (Jones & Dangl, 2006). In one scenario, the product of the *Avr* effector gene binds
 620 to the product of the *R* gene (a receptor) to activate host resistance mechanisms. In another scenario, the
 621 product of the *Avr* effector gene binds to an essential host target which is guarded by the product of the *R*
 622 gene (a receptor). Once *Avr* effector binding is detected, host resistance mechanisms are activated. The
 623 absence of the *Avr* effector product or the absence of the *R* gene product leads to susceptibility (a
 624 compatible interaction). The small black dot indicates no disease formation, and the large black oval
 625 indicates full disease formation, and (d) an inverse gene-for-gene genetic relationship. Again, considerable
 626 specificity is observed based on the interaction of a pathogen necrotrophic effector (NE) with a host
 627 susceptibility (*S*) target to determine specific recognition. The product of the pathogen NE gene binds to the
 628 product of the *S* gene (a receptor) to activate host susceptibility mechanisms.
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Figure 3. Conceptual model showing the relationship between metagenotypes, genotypes and annotations. The curator selects a pathogen genotype and a host genotype to combine into a metagenotype. The metagenotype can be annotated with pathogen–host interaction phenotypes from PHIPO (the Pathogen–Host Interaction Phenotype Ontology).

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639 **Figure 4.** PHI-Canto curation workflow diagram. This diagram shows the curation workflow from the start of
640 a curation session to its submission. The PubMed ID of the publication to be curated is entered and the title
641 is automatically retrieved. The curator enters their name, email address and ORCID ID. On the species and
642 genes page, the experimental pathogen and host genes are entered using UniProtKB accession numbers,
643 and for experiments where a mutant pathogen genotype is assayed on a wild type host with no specified
644 genes, there is the option to select the host species from an autocomplete menu. Information on the
645 specific experimental strains used for each species is entered. After entering this initial information, the
646 curator follows one of three distinct workflows depending on the biological feature the user wants to
647 annotate (metagenotype, genotype or gene annotation type). Except for genes, biological features are
648 created by composing less complex features: genotypes from alleles (generated in the pathogen or host
649 genotype management pages), and metagenotypes from genotypes (generated in the metagenotype
650 management page). Biological features are annotated with terms from a controlled vocabulary (usually an
651 ontology), plus additional information that varies based on the annotation type. The curator has the option
652 to generate further annotations after creating one, but this iterative process is not represented in the

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diagram for the sake of brevity. After all annotations have been made, the session is submitted into PHI-base version 5. * Note that the 'Ontology annotation' group covers multiple annotation types, all of which annotate biological features with terms from an ontology or controlled vocabulary. These annotation types are described in Table 1.

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Figure 5. Network diagram showing the data resources used by PHI-Canto. Of the databases shown, PHI-base provides data (experimental conditions, disease names and species strain names) used to create terms in the PHI-base controlled vocabularies; UniProtKB provides accession numbers for proteins that PHI-Canto uses to identify genes; and the NCBI Taxonomy database is used to generate a mapping file relating taxonomic identifiers lower than species rank to their nearest taxonomic identifiers at species rank. The OBO ontologies group contains ontologies in the OBO format that PHI-Canto uses for its annotation types. The parenthesized text after the ontology name indicates the term prefix for the ontology.

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Figure 6. The interspecies curation framework and the interoperability of PHI-Canto.

The interspecies curation framework consists of three main components. Firstly, a curation tool called PHI-Canto (The Pathogen–Host Interaction Community Annotation Tool), secondly, a new species neutral phenotype ontology called PHIPO (the Pathogen–Host Interaction Phenotype Ontology), and thirdly, a selection of additional controlled vocabularies for disease names (PHIDO), experimental conditions (PHI-ECO), pathogen and host species, and natural strains associated with each species. The two-way arrows indicate that terms from the ontology and controlled vocabularies are used in curation with PHI-Canto, and that new terms required for curation may be suggested for inclusion within the ontology and controlled vocabularies. (b) The PHI-Canto and PHIPO content curation framework (grey box) uses persistent identifiers and cross-referenced information from UniProt, Ensembl Genomes and the Gene Ontology. PHIPO is made available at the OBO Foundry. Newly minted wild type gene annotations are suggested for inclusion into the Gene Ontology via the EBI Gene Ontology Annotation database. Data curated in PHI-Canto, following expert review, is then shared with ELIXIR data resources such as UniProtKB, Ensembl Genomes, FungiDB, and KnetMiner, and provided on request to other databases (FgMutantDB, GloBI). Researchers can look up curated information via the PHI-base web interface or can download the whole dataset from PHI-base for inclusion in their bioinformatics pipelines. Authors can submit data to PHI-base by curating their publications into PHI-Canto. The origin of data is indicated by directional arrows.

Figure 7. Top 25 Journals in PHI-base.

Bar chart showing the top 25 journals by number of publications curated in PHI-base, as of version 4.13 (published 9 May 2022). Publication counts were generated by extracting every unique PubMed identifier (PMID) from PHI-base, then using the Entrez Programming Utilities (E-Utilities) to retrieve the journal name for each PMID, and finally summing the count of journal names. The total number of journals in version 4.13 of PHI-base was 291.

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Table 1. Annotation types and annotation extensions in PHI-Canto, grouped by the biological feature being annotated.

Annotation type	Annotation extensions ¹	Annotation value
Annotation types for the <i>gene</i> biological feature ²		
Gene Ontology annotation		Gene Ontology term
	with host species	NCBI Taxonomy ID
	with symbiont species	NCBI Taxonomy ID
Wild type expression		PomBase Gene Expression ontology term
	during	Gene Ontology biological process term ³
	in presence of	Chemical entity (ChEBI ontology)
	tissue type	BRENDA Tissue Ontology term
Annotation types for the <i>genotype</i> biological feature		
Single species phenotype (Pathogen phenotype or Host phenotype)		PHIPO term (single-species phenotype branch)
	affected proteins	UniProtKB accession number (one for each affected protein)
	assayed RNA	UniProtKB accession number
	assayed protein	UniProtKB accession number
	observed in organ	BRENDA Tissue Ontology term ⁴
	penetrance	Qualitative value (low, normal, high, complete) or quantitative value (percentage)
	severity	Qualitative value (low, normal, high, variable) or quantitative value (percentage)
Annotation types for the <i>metagenotype</i> biological feature		
Pathogen–host interaction phenotype or Gene-for-gene phenotype		PHIPO term (pathogen–host interaction phenotype branch)
	affected proteins	UniProtKB accession number (one for each affected protein)
	assayed protein	UniProtKB accession number
	assayed RNA	UniProtKB accession number
	compared to control metagenotype	Metagenotype ⁵
	extent of infectivity ⁶	PHIPO term
	gene-for-gene interaction ⁷	PHIPO Extension (PHIPO_EXT) ontology term
	host tissue infected	BRENDA Tissue Ontology term
	inverse gene-for-gene interaction ⁷	PHIPO Extension (PHIPO_EXT) ontology term
	outcome of interaction ⁶	PHIPO term
	penetrance	Qualitative value (low, normal, high, complete) or quantitative value (percentage)
	severity	Qualitative value (low, normal, high) or quantitative value (percentage)
Disease name		PHIDO term ⁸
	host tissue infected	BRENDA Tissue Ontology term

¹ PHI-Canto uses 44 annotation extension (AE) relations, of which 9 are unique to PHI-base, while the remaining 35 are shared with PomBase.

² Additional AEs shared with PomBase for the gene annotation types are available in Supplementary file 2.

³ Restricted to GO:0022403, GO:0033554, GO:0072690, GO:0051707 and their descendant terms.

⁴ Restricted to BTO:0001489, BTO:0001494, BTO:0001461 and their descendant terms.

⁵ Metagenotypes are selected from those already added to the curation session.

⁶ AE only applies to pathogen–host interaction phenotypes.

⁷ AE only applies to gene-for-gene phenotypes. ⁸ Curated list of disease names.

Table 2. Publications selected for trial curation using PHI-Canto.

Subject of publication	PMID	Publication title	Genotype ¹⁰ annotated with	Metagenotype ¹¹ annotated with
Bacteria–human interaction	28715477 ¹	The RhlR quorum-sensing receptor controls <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> pathogenesis and biofilm development independently of its canonical homoserine lactone autoinducer.	Pathogen phenotype	unaffected pathogenicity altered pathogenicity or virulence
Fungal–human interaction/novel antifungal target	28720735 ²	A nonredundant phosphopantetheinyl transferase, PptA, is a novel antifungal target that directs secondary metabolite, siderophore, and lysine biosynthesis in <i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> and is critical for pathogenicity.	Pathogen phenotype	unaffected pathogenicity altered pathogenicity or virulence
Secondary metabolite clusters required for pathogen virulence	30459352 ²	Phosphopantetheinyl transferase (Ppt)-mediated biosynthesis of lysine, but not siderophores or DHN melanin, is required for virulence of <i>Zymoseptoria tritici</i> on wheat.	Pathogen phenotype	unaffected pathogenicity altered pathogenicity or virulence
Early acting virulence proteins	29020037 ^{2,3}	A conserved fungal glycosyltransferase facilitates pathogenesis of plants by enabling hyphal growth on solid surfaces.	Pathogen phenotype	altered pathogenicity or virulence
Mutualism interaction	16517760 ⁴	Reactive oxygen species play a role in regulating a fungus-perennial ryegrass mutualistic interaction	Pathogen phenotype	mutualism
First host targets of pathogen effectors	31804478 ^{2,5}	An effector protein of the wheat stripe rust fungus targets chloroplasts and suppresses chloroplast function.	N/A	altered pathogenicity or virulence a pathogen effector
Receptor decoys	30220500 ⁵	Suppression of plant immunity by fungal chitinase-like effectors.	Pathogen phenotype	a pathogen effector
R-Avr interactions	20601497 ^{6,7}	Activation of an Arabidopsis resistance protein is specified by the <i>in planta</i> association of its leucine-rich repeat domain with the cognate oomycete effector.	Host phenotype	a pathogen effector a gene-for-gene interaction
Fungal toxins required for virulence on plants	22241993 ⁸	The cysteine rich necrotrophic effector SnTox1 produced by <i>Stagonospora nodorum</i> triggers susceptibility of wheat lines harboring Snn1.	N/A	a pathogen effector a gene-for-gene interaction (inverse)
Resistance to antifungal chemistries	22314539 ⁹	The T788G mutation in the cyp51C gene confers voriconazole resistance in <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> causing aspergillosis.	Pathogen phenotype Pathogen chemistry phenotype	N/A

¹ Example of curating 'unaffected pathogenicity' available in Appendix 1.² Example of curating 'altered pathogenicity or virulence' available in Appendix 1 and Appendix 2.³ Example of 'in vitro pathogen phenotype' available in Appendix 1.⁴ Example of curating 'mutualism' available in Appendix 1. Although 'mutualism interactions' are generally out of scope for PHI-base, PHI-Canto can be used to curate these publications if required. In this study, the fungal gene mutation altered the interaction from mutualistic to antagonistic.⁵ Example of curating 'a pathogen effector' available in Appendix 1.⁶ Example of curating 'a gene-for-gene interaction' available in Appendix 1.⁷ Example of 'in vivo host phenotype' available in Appendix 1.⁸ Example of curating 'an inverse gene-for-gene interaction' available in Appendix 1.⁹ Example of 'in vitro pathogen chemistry phenotype' available in Appendix 1.¹⁰ Single species genotypes could be annotated with either a pathogen phenotype, a pathogen chemistry phenotype, or a host phenotype. Genotypes are annotated with *in vitro* or *in vivo* phenotypes from PHIPO, using either the Pathogen phenotype or Host phenotype annotation type workflow.¹¹ Metagenotype comprises of a pathogen and a host genotype in combination. Phenotypes from PHIPO can be annotated to metagenotypes using either the 'Pathogen–Host Interaction Phenotype' or 'Gene-for-Gene Phenotype' annotation type workflow.

728
729**Table 3.** Issues encountered whilst curating ten example publications with PHI-Canto.

Curated feature	Problem description	Solution	Context in PHI-Canto	Example
Species strain	UniProtKB sequence information is commonly from a reference genome strain. This sequence may differ from the experimental strain curated in PHI-Canto.	Develop a selectable list of strains for curators to assign to the genotype (and metagenotype).	Strain selected after UniProtKB entry on gene entry page. Strain used within genotype creation.	URL ¹ All phenotype annotation examples in Appendix 1 contain a 'strain name' within the genotype / metagenotype.
Delivery mechanism	Pathogen–host interaction experiments use a wide array of mechanisms to deliver the treatment of choice (to cells, tissues, and host and non-host species) which are required for experimental interpretation.	Develop terms prefixed with 'delivery mechanism' in the Pathogen–Host Interaction Experimental Conditions Ontology (PHI-ECO).	Selection of experimental conditions whilst making a phenotype annotation to a metagenotype.	URL ² Examples in Appendix 1 PMID:20601497, PMID:31804478 and PMID:22241993.
Physical interaction	Physical interactions (i.e., protein–protein interactions) could only be annotated between proteins of the same species, so it was not possible to annotate interactions between a pathogen effector and its first host target.	Adapt the 'Physical Interaction' annotation type to store gene and species information from two organisms (instead of one).	Physical Interaction annotation type.	URL ³
Pathogen effector	There was no available ontology term to describe a 'class' pathogen effector (a 'transferred entity from pathogen to host'), because effectors have heterogeneous functions (specific enzyme inhibitors, modulating host immune responses, and targeting host gene-silencing mechanisms). Effector is not a phenotype, and so did not fit into the Pathogen–Host Interaction Phenotype Ontology (PHIPO).	Develop new Gene Ontology (GO) biological process terms (and children), to group 'effector-mediated' processes.	GO Biological Process annotation on a pathogen gene.	URL ⁴ Example in Appendix 1 PMID:31804478.
Wild type control phenotypes	Natural sequence variation between strains of both pathogen and host organisms can alter the phenotypic outcome within an interaction. The wild type metagenotype phenotype needs to be curated so that the phenotype of an altered metagenotype is informative.	Allow creation of metagenotypes containing wild type genes. Develop a new annotation extension (AE) property 'compared to control', used in annotation of altered metagenotypes.	Annotation of phenotypes and AEs to metagenotypes (using the 'PHI phenotype' or 'Gene for Gene phenotype' annotation type).	URL ⁵ Examples in Appendix 1 PMID:28715477, PMID:16517760, PMID:29020037, PMID:20601497, PMID:22241993.
Chemistry	How to record chemicals for resistance or sensitivity phenotypes.	Follow PomBase model to pre-compose PHIPO terms to include chemical names from the ChEBI ontology.	Annotation of phenotypes to single species genotypes.	URL ⁴ Example in Appendix 1 PMID:22314539.
Gene for gene interactions	Complex gene-for-gene interactions within plant pathogen–host interactions required additional detail to describe the function of the pathogen and host genes within the metagenotype (including the specified strains).	Develop the additional metagenotype curation type 'Gene for Gene Phenotype'. Develop two new AEs, 'gene_for_gene_interaction' and 'inverse gene_for_gene_interaction', using PHIPO_EXT terms describing three components of the interaction.	Annotation of phenotypes and AEs to metagenotypes using the 'Gene for Gene Phenotype' annotation type.	URL ⁴ Examples in Appendix 1 PMID:20601497 and PMID:22241993.
Nine high-level legacy terms (from PHI-base 4)	PHI-base should incorporate legacy data from PHI-base 4 into new PHI-base 5 gene-centric pages.	Maintain the nine high level terms as 'tags' within the new PHI-base 5 user interface. Develop mapping methods to enable this.	Three locations described in Supplementary file 3.	Urban et al., 2015 NAR (PMID:25414340).

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¹Namely, i) the compatibility of the interaction ii) the functional status of the pathogen gene and iii) the functional status of the host gene.
 URL¹ https://canto.phi-base.org/docs/getting_started#adding_strains, URL² https://canto.phi-base.org/docs/phipo_annotation#experimental_conditions, URL³ https://canto.phi-base.org/docs/physical_interaction_annotation,
 URL⁴ https://canto.phi-base.org/docs/phipo_annotation#pathogen_host_interaction_phenotypes, URL⁵ https://canto.phi-base.org/docs/genotypes#metagenotype_management

735 **Table 4.** Automatically and manually curated types of data displayed in gene-centric PHI-base 5.
736

Data type	Data source
Metadata	
Entry Summary ¹	UniProtKB ²
Pathogen species	NCBI Taxonomy ²
Pathogen strain	PHI-base strain list
Host species	NCBI Taxonomy ²
Host strain	PHI-base strain list
Publication	PubMed ²
Phenotype annotation sections	
Pathogen–Host Interaction Phenotype	PHIPO ³ pathogen–host interaction phenotype branch
Gene-for-Gene Phenotype	PHIPO pathogen–host interaction phenotype branch
Pathogen Phenotype	PHIPO single species phenotype branch
Host Phenotype	PHIPO single species phenotype branch
Other annotation sections	
Disease name	PHIDO
GO Molecular Function	GO ⁴
GO Biological Process	GO
GO Cellular Component	GO
Wild type RNA level	FYPO_EXT ⁵
Wild type Protein level	FYPO_EXT
Physical Interaction	BioGRID ⁶
Protein Modification	PSI-MOD ⁷

737 ¹ The Entry Summary section includes information on which gene is being displayed in the gene-centric
738 results page. The UniProtKB accession number is used to automatically retrieve the name and function of
739 the protein, plus any cross-referenced identifiers from Ensembl Genomes and NCBI GenBank. The
740 section also displays the PHI-base 5 gene identifier (PHIG) and any of the high-level terms
741 (Supplementary file 3) annotated to the gene.

742 ² Data from UniProtKB, NCBI Taxonomy and PubMed are automatically retrieved, while all other data are
743 manually curated.

744 ³ PHIPO is the Pathogen–Host Interaction Phenotype Ontology.

745 ⁴ GO is the Gene Ontology.

746 ⁵ FYPO_EXT is the Fission Yeast Phenotype Ontology Extension.

747 ⁶ BioGRID is the Biological General Repository for Interaction Datasets.

748 ⁷ PSI-MOD is the Human Proteome Organization (HUPO) Proteomics Standards Initiative (PSI) Protein
749 Modifications Ontology.

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751

752 Figure supplements (at end of this document)

753 **Figure 3 – figure supplement 1.** Canto entity relationship model.

754 Simplified UML class diagram showing the relations between entities (things of interest) in a
755 Canto curation session. The numbers on the connecting lines represent the cardinality of the
756 relation, meaning how many of one entity can be related to another entity: 0..n means 'zero or
757 more'; 1..n means 'one or more'. Lines with a hollow arrowhead indicate that the target entity (at
758 the head of the arrow) is a generalization of the source entity (at the tail of the arrow). Boxes
759 outlined in bold indicate new entities which were added to support curation in PHI-Canto.

760

761 **Figure 3 – figure supplement 2.** Entity–relationship model for the main Canto database.

762 This database stores data that is shared across all curation sessions. Database tables are
763 represented as boxes, and arrows between boxes indicate a connection between tables. The
764 table and property names contain numerous abbreviations, which are expanded as follows:
765 curs: curation session, pub: publication, db: database, xref: cross-reference, cv: controlled
766 vocabulary.

767

768 **Figure 3 – figure supplement 3.** Entity–relationship model for a Canto curation session
769 database.

770 This database stores data that is unique to a curation session. Database tables are represented
771 as boxes, and arrows between boxes indicate a connection between tables. The 'pub' table
772 stands for 'publication'.

773

774 **Figure 4 – figure supplement 1.** Alternative curation step workflow.

775 The flow diagram represents the PHI-Canto curation process from beginning to end in 5 steps.

776 This diagram is an alternative representation to the image depicted in Figure 4. During step 2 of
777 the workflow, the curator chooses either the gene annotation or genotype / metagenotype
778 annotation process. Multiple annotations can be made using both annotation processes which
779 can then be submitted for review.

780

781 **Figure 4 – figure supplement 2.** What you need to curate a publication into PHI-Canto.

782 **Figure 4 – figure supplement 3.** Instructions on how to look up a UniProtKB ID.

783 **Figure 5 – figure supplement 1.** Resources relied upon by PHI-Canto.

784 Supplementary files

785 **Supplementary file 1.** Mapping display name to relation name for Annotation Extensions in
786 PHI-Canto.

787 **Supplementary file 2.** PomBase annotation extensions also used in PHI-Canto.

788 **Supplementary file 3.** PHI-base nine high level term mapping to PHI-Canto.

789 **Supplementary file 4.** PHI-Canto species and strain lists for pathogens and hosts.

790 **Supplementary file 5.** Mapping between strains in PHI-base and PHI-Canto.

791 Source code

792 **Source code 1.** Main configuration file for PHI-Canto.

793 This is the main configuration file for PHI-Canto. Much of the configuration is inherited from
794 Canto, the original curation application from which PHI-Canto is derived. Lines containing
795 custom configuration for PHI-Canto have been indicated with comments.
796

797 Appendix 1. How to use Annotation Extensions.

798 This file provides information on Annotation Extensions (AE) and how to use them in PHI-Canto
799 to curate a standard selection of experiments (Table 2). The first section provides four examples
800 of using AEs for curating metagenotypes with pathogen-host interaction phenotypes. The
801 second section provides examples of curating metagenotypes using the gene-for-gene
802 phenotype workflow, including using the AEs for gene-for-gene interactions and inverse gene-
803 for-gene interactions. The third section of this file illustrates three examples of using AEs for
804 curating single species phenotypes.

805 Further information on how to use PHI-Canto to make annotations can be found in PHI-Canto's
806 user documentation, available at <https://canto.phi-base.org/docs/index>.

807 Contents:

808 SECTION 1: Annotation Extensions for curating pathogen-host interaction phenotypes on metagenotypes

- 809 • Section 1A: If you have a metagenotype phenotype recording 'unaffected pathogenicity'
810 (corresponds to footnote 1 in Table 2)
- 811 • Section 1B: If you have a metagenotype phenotype recording 'altered pathogenicity or virulence'
812 (corresponds to footnote 2 in Table 2)
- 813 • Section 1C: If you have a metagenotype phenotype recording 'mutualism' (corresponds to
814 footnote 4 in Table 2)
- 815 • Section 1D: If you have a metagenotype phenotype recording 'a pathogen effector' (corresponds
816 to footnote 5 in Table 2)

817
818 SECTION 2: Annotation Extensions for curating gene-for-gene phenotypes on metagenotypes

- 819 • Section 2A: If you have a metagenotype phenotype recording 'a gene-for-gene interaction'
820 (corresponds to footnote 6 in Table 2)
- 821 • Section 2B: If you have a metagenotype phenotype recording 'an inverse gene-for-gene
822 interaction' (corresponds to footnote 8 in Table 2)

823
824 SECTION 3: Annotation Extensions for curating single species phenotypes (pathogen phenotypes or host
825 phenotypes)

- 826 • Section 3A: Example of an in vitro pathogen phenotype (corresponds to footnote 3 in Table 2)
- 827 • Section 3B: Example of an in vitro pathogen chemistry phenotype (corresponds to footnote 9 in
828 Table 2)
- 829 • Section 3C: Example of an in vivo host phenotype (corresponds to footnote 7 in Table 2)

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832

833 SECTION 1: Annotation Extensions for curating pathogen-host
 834 interaction phenotypes on metagenotypes

835 When creating and annotating metagenotypes, it is advisable to also create and annotate a wild
 836 type control metagenotype where possible. This enables a better understanding of annotations
 837 made to altered metagenotypes.

838 (Note: it is also possible to use several of the AEs in the table documenting single species
 839 phenotype AEs, e.g. *penetrance* and *affected protein*)

840 Section 1A: If you have a metagenotype phenotype recording ‘unaffected
 841 pathogenicity’ (corresponds to footnote 1 in Table 2)

842 Appendix 1 – table 1 Annotation Extensions (AE) summary for ‘unaffected
 843 pathogenicity’

AE name	Cardinality	Available terms
compared to control genotype	0, 1	Metagenotype identifier
extent of infectivity	0, 1	‘unaffected pathogenicity’
host tissue affected	0, <i>n</i>	BRENDA Tissue Ontology term
outcome of interaction	0, 1	‘disease present’, ‘disease absent’

844 Example publication: The RhIR quorum-sensing receptor controls *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*
 845 pathogenesis and biofilm development independently of its canonical homoserine lactone
 846 autoinducer. ([PMID:28715477](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28715477/))

847 Appendix 1 – figure 1 Pathogen-host interaction phenotype for ‘unaffected
 848 pathogenicity’

849 Control metagenotype

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
rhII+[WT level] <i>P. aeruginosa</i> (PA14)	wild type <i>C. elegans</i> (N2)	PHIPO:0001069	death of host organism with pathogen	Cell growth assay	agar plates	Fig 6a	infects_tissue whole body , has_penetrance 50% , interaction_outcome disease present

850

851 Altered metagenotype

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
<i>rhIIΔ</i> <i>P. aeruginosa</i> (PA14)	wild type <i>C. elegans</i> (N2)	PHIPO:0001069	death of host organism with pathogen	Cell growth assay	agar plates	Fig 6a	infects_tissue whole body , infective_ability unaffected pathogenicity , has_penetrance 50% , compared_to_control rhII+[WT level] <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (PA14) / wild type <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> (N2) , interaction_outcome disease present

852

853 Note: Phenotype annotations use evidence codes modeled on the Evidence & Conclusion
854 Ontology (ECO). Evidence code 'Cell growth assay' corresponds to 'cell growth assay evidence'
855 (ECO:0001563).

856

857 Section 1B: If you have a metagenotype phenotype recording 'altered
858 pathogenicity or virulence' (corresponds to footnote 2 in Table 2)

859 Appendix 1 – table 2 Annotation Extensions (AE) summary for 'altered pathogenicity or
860 virulence'

AE name	Cardinality	Available terms
compared to control genotype	0, 1	Metagenotype identifier
extent of infectivity	0, 1	'loss of pathogenicity', 'reduced virulence', 'increased virulence'
host tissue affected	0, <i>n</i>	BRENDA Tissue Ontology term
outcome of interaction	0, 1	'disease present', 'disease absent'

861 Example publication: A conserved fungal glycosyltransferase facilitates pathogenesis of plants
862 by enabling hyphal growth on solid surfaces ([PMID:29020037](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29020037/))

863 A training video is available for the curation of this publication at
864 <https://youtu.be/44XGoi6ljqk?t=1738>

865 Appendix 1 – figure 2 Pathogen-host interaction phenotype for 'altered pathogenicity or
866 virulence'

867 Control metagenotype

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
GT2+[WT level] <i>Z. tritici</i> (IPO323)	wild type <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Riband)	PHIPO:0000480	presence of pathogen-associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	14 days post inoculation	Figure 2E	infects_tissue leaf , interaction_outcome disease present

868

869 Altered metagenotype

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
ΔGT2-19(deletion) <i>Z. tritici</i> (IPO323)	wild type <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Riband)	PHIPO:0000481	absence of pathogen-associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	14 days post inoculation	Figure 2E	infects_tissue leaf , infective_ability loss of pathogenicity , compared_to_control GT2+[WT level] Zymoseptoria tritici (IPO323) / wild type Triticum aestivum (cv. Riband) , interaction_outcome disease absent

870

871 Note: Phenotype annotations use evidence codes modeled on ECO. Evidence code
872 'Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)' corresponds to the new ECO term
873 'qualitative macroscopy evidence' (ECO:0006342).

874 Section 1C: If you have a metagenotype phenotype recording 'mutualism'
875 (corresponds to footnote 4 in Table 2)

876 Appendix 1 – table 3 Annotation Extensions (AE) summary for 'mutualism'

AE name	Cardinality	Available terms
compared to control genotype	0, 1	Metagenotype identifier
extent of infectivity	0, 1	'mutualism present', 'mutualism absent', 'loss of mutualism'
host tissue affected	0, <i>n</i>	BRENDA Tissue Ontology term

877 Note: The 'Outcome of interaction' AE is not relevant in this mutualism interaction.

878 Example publication: Reactive oxygen species play a role in regulating a fungus-perennial
879 ryegrass mutualistic interaction ([PMID:16517760](#))

880 Appendix 1 – figure 3 Pathogen-host interaction phenotype: Example 1

881 Illustrating a phenotype associated with the pathogen component within the Pathogen-Host
882 Interaction.

883 Control metagenotype

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Figure	Annotation extension
noxA+[WT level] <i>E. festucae</i> (F1) bkg: GFP	wild type <i>L. perenne</i> (Unknown strain)	PHIPO:0000954	presence of pathogen growth within host	Microscopy	Figure 1c	infects_tissue leaf , infective_ability mutualism present

884

885 Altered metagenotype

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Figure	Annotation extension
noxA::pAN7-1(disruption)[Not assayed] <i>E. festucae</i> (F1) bkg: GFP	wild type <i>L. perenne</i> (Unknown strain)	PHIPO:0000368	increased pathogen growth within host	Microscopy	Figure 1d	infects_tissue leaf , infective_ability loss of mutualism , compared_to_control noxA+[WT level] <i>Epichloe festucae</i> (F1) / wild type <i>Lolium perenne</i> (Unknown strain)

886

887 Note: Phenotype annotations use evidence codes modeled on ECO. Evidence code
888 'Microscopy' corresponds to 'microscopy evidence' (ECO:0001098).

889 Appendix 1 – figure 4 Pathogen-host interaction phenotype: Example 2

890 Illustrating a phenotype associated with the host component within the Pathogen-Host
891 Interaction.

892 Control metagenotype

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Figure	Annotation extension
noxA+[WT level] <i>E. festucae</i> (F1)	wild type <i>L. perenne</i> (Unknown strain)	PHIPO:0001005	normal host morphology during pathogen invasion	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	Figure 1a, 5c	infects_tissue whole plant , infective_ability mutualism present

893

894 Altered metagenotype

895 Note: in this case, two separate annotations were made to the same metagenotype.

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Figure	Annotation extension
noxA::pAN7-1(disruption)[Not assayed] <i>E. festucae</i> (F1)	wild type <i>L. perenne</i> (Unknown strain)	PHIPO:0001130	stunted host growth during pathogen colonization	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	Figure 1a	infects_tissue whole plant , infective_ability loss of mutualism , compared_to_control noxA+[WT level] <i>Epichloe festucae</i> (F1) / wild type <i>Lolium perenne</i> (Unknown strain)

896

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Figure	Annotation extension
noxA::pAN7-1(disruption)[Not assayed] <i>E. festucae</i> (F1)	wild type <i>L. perenne</i> (Unknown strain)	PHIPO:0001131	increased number of host side shoots during pathogen colonization	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	Figure 1a	infects_tissue whole plant , infective_ability loss of mutualism , compared_to_control noxA+[WT level] <i>Epichloe festucae</i> (F1) / wild type <i>Lolium perenne</i> (Unknown strain)

897

898 Section 1D: If you have a metagenotype phenotype recording 'a pathogen
899 effector' (corresponds to footnote 5 in Table 2)

900 If you have a biotrophic or necrotrophic plant pathogen effector which is involved in a gene-for-
901 gene interaction, please see the AEs for the 'gene-for-gene interaction' or 'inverse gene-for-
902 gene interaction' workflow (Section 2).

903 Annotate the pathogen effector with the GO Biological Process term 'effector-mediated
904 modulation of host process by symbiont' ([GO:0140418](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ontology/term/GO:0140418)) or a descendant. If the GO Molecular

905 Function term is known, then this can also be annotated and linked to the relevant GO effector
 906 term via an annotation extension.

907 Appendix 1 – table 4 Annotation Extensions (AE) summary for ‘a pathogen effector’

AE name	Cardinality	Available terms
compared to control genotype	0, 1	Metagenotype identifier
extent of infectivity	0, 1	‘unaffected pathogenicity’, ‘loss of pathogenicity’, ‘reduced virulence’, ‘increased virulence’
host tissue affected	0, <i>n</i>	BRENDA Tissue Ontology term
outcome of interaction	0, 1	‘disease present’, ‘disease absent’

908 Example publication: An effector protein of the wheat stripe rust fungus targets chloroplasts and
 909 suppresses chloroplast function. ([PMID:31804478](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31804478/))

910 Appendix 1 – figure 5 Gene Ontology (GO) biological process annotation for ‘a
 911 pathogen effector’

Species	Gene	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Figure
<i>P. striiformis</i>	PSTG_12806	GO:0052034	effector-mediated suppression of host pattern-triggered immunity	IDA	Figure 3a

912

913 Note: ‘effector-mediated suppression of host pattern-triggered immunity’ ([GO:0052034](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ontology/term/GO:0052034)) is a
 914 descendant term of ‘effector-mediated modulation of host process by symbiont’ ([GO:0140418](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ontology/term/GO:0140418)).

915 Note: GO annotations use GO evidence codes ([http://geneontology.org/docs/guide-go-
 916 evidence-codes/](http://geneontology.org/docs/guide-go-evidence-codes/)).

917

918 Appendix 1 – figure 6 Gene Ontology (GO) molecular function annotation for ‘a
 919 pathogen effector’

Species	Gene	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	With	Figure	Annotation extension
<i>P. striiformis</i>	PSTG_12806	GO:0005515	protein binding	IPI	petC	Figure 5	part_of effector-mediated suppression of host pattern-triggered immunity
<i>P. striiformis</i>	PSTG_12806	GO:0004857	enzyme inhibitor activity	IPI	petC	Figure 5	has_regulation_target petC , occurs_at host cell chloroplast , part_of effector-mediated suppression of host pattern-triggered immunity

920

921 Please note that in the case of a physical interaction (protein–protein interaction) between the
 922 pathogen and host gene products (PSTG_12806 and PetC in the example above, respectively)
 923 this information can be curated using the Physical Interaction curation workflow, documented in
 924 https://canto.phi-base.org/docs/physical_interaction_annotation.

925 Appendix 1 – figure 7 Pathogen-host interaction phenotypes for ‘a pathogen effector’

926 Control metagenotype

927 In this case, there are no metagenotype control annotations. This is because it is not possible to
928 create and annotate a metagenotype comprising of an empty vector control within the pathogen
929 component of the metagenotype.

930 Altered metagenotype

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID ↕	Term name ↕	Evidence code ↕	Conditions	Figure ↕	Annotation extension ↕
Pst_12806ΔSP(1-23)[Not assayed] <i>P. striiformis</i> (f. sp. tritici strain CYR32)	wild type <i>N. benthamiana</i> (Unknown strain)	PHIPO:0001015	decreased level of host defense-induced callose deposition	Microscopy	delivery mechanism: agrobacterium, + PTI inducer flg22	Figure 3a, b	infects_tissue leaf , infective_ability increased virulence
Pst_12806ΔSP(1-23)[Not assayed] <i>P. striiformis</i> (f. sp. tritici strain CYR32)	wild type <i>N. benthamiana</i> (Unknown strain)	PHIPO:0001128	effector-mediated suppression of host PAMP-triggered immunity present	Microscopy	delivery mechanism: agrobacterium, + PTI inducer flg22	Figure 3a, b, c	infective_ability increased virulence

931

932

933 **SECTION 2: Annotation Extensions for curating gene-for-gene**
 934 **phenotypes on metagenotypes**

935 Section 2A: If you have a metagenotype phenotype recording ‘a gene-for-
 936 gene interaction’ (corresponds to footnote 6 in Table 2)

937 Annotate the pathogen effector with the GO Biological process term ‘effector-mediated
 938 modulation of host process by symbiont’ ([GO:0140418](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ontology/lookup?term=GO:0140418)) or a descendant. If the GO Molecular
 939 Function term is known, then this can also be annotated and linked to the relevant GO effector
 940 term via an annotation extension.

941 Appendix 1 – table 5 Annotation Extensions (AE) summary for ‘a gene-for-gene
 942 interaction’

AE name	Cardinality	Available terms
compared to control genotype	0, 1	Metagenotype identifier
gene-for-gene phenotype	0, 1	‘incompatible interaction, recognizable pathogen effector present, functional host resistance gene present’ ‘incompatible interaction, recognizable pathogen effector present, gain of functional host resistance gene’ ‘incompatible interaction, gain of recognizable pathogen effector, gain of functional host resistance gene’ ‘incompatible interaction, gain of recognizable pathogen effector, functional host resistance gene present’

		<p>'compatible interaction, recognizable pathogen effector present, functional host resistance gene absent'</p> <p>'compatible interaction, recognizable pathogen effector absent, functional host resistance gene present'</p> <p>'compatible interaction, recognizable pathogen effector present, compromised host resistance gene'</p> <p>'compatible interaction, recognizable pathogen effector absent, functional host resistance gene absent'</p> <p>'compatible interaction, recognizable pathogen effector absent, compromised functional host resistance gene'</p> <p>'compatible interaction, compromised recognizable pathogen effector, functional host resistance gene present'</p> <p>'metagenotype outcome overcome by external condition'</p>
host tissue affected	0, <i>n</i>	BRENDA Tissue Ontology term

943 Example publication: Activation of an Arabidopsis resistance protein is specified by the in planta
 944 association of its leucine-rich repeat domain with the cognate oomycete effector.
 945 ([PMID:20601497](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20601497/)).

946 Appendix 1 – figure 8 Gene Ontology (GO) biological process annotation for ‘a
 947 pathogen effector’ within ‘a gene-for-gene interaction’

Species	Gene	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code
<i>H. arabidopsidis</i>	ATR1	GO:0140418	effector-mediated modulation of host process by symbiont	IMP

948

949 Appendix 1 – figure 9 Gene Ontology (GO) molecular function annotation for ‘a
 950 pathogen effector’ within ‘a gene-for-gene interaction’

Species	Gene	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	With	Figure	Annotation extension
<i>H. arabidopsidis</i>	ATR1	GO:0005515	protein binding	IPI	RPP1	Figure 4, 5	part_of effector-mediated modulation of host process by symbiont

951

952 Appendix 1 – figure 10 Gene-for-gene phenotype

953 Control metagenotypes

954 *Incompatible control*

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
ATR1-Δ51(1-51)[Not assayed] <i>H. arabidopsidis</i> (Maks9) bkg: Citrine tag	RPP1+[Not assayed] <i>A. thaliana</i> (ecotype Ws-0) bkg: HA tag	PHIPO:0000192	presence of host-defense induced lesion by host hypersensitive response	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	delivery mechanism: agrobacterium, heterologous species tobacco	Figure 3a	infects_tissue leaf , gene_for_gene_interaction incompatible interaction, recognizable pathogen effector present, functional host resistance gene present

955

956 *Compatible control*

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
ATR1-Δ51(1-51)[Not assayed] <i>H. arabidopsidis</i> (Maks9) bkg: Citrine tag	RPP1+[Not assayed] <i>A. thaliana</i> (ecotype Nd-0) bkg: HA tag	PHIPO:0000182	absence of host-defense induced lesion by host hypersensitive response	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	delivery mechanism: agrobacterium, heterologous species tobacco	Figure 3b, 8b	infects_tissue leaf , gene_for_gene_interaction compatible interaction, recognizable pathogen effector absent, functional host resistance gene present

957

958 **Altered metagenotype (shift from compatible to incompatible interaction)**

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
ATR1-Δ51-D191G(1-51, D191G)[Not assayed] <i>H. arabidopsidis</i> (Maks9) bkg: Citrine tag	RPP1+[Not assayed] <i>A. thaliana</i> (ecotype Nd-0) bkg: HA tag	PHIPO:0000192	presence of host-defense induced lesion by host hypersensitive response	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	delivery mechanism: agrobacterium, heterologous species tobacco	Figure 8b	infects_tissue leaf , gene_for_gene_interaction incompatible interaction, gain of recognizable pathogen effector, functional host resistance gene present , compared_to_control ATR1-delta51(1-51)[Not assayed] Hyaloperonospora arabidopsidis (Maks9) / RPP1+[Not assayed] Arabidopsis thaliana (ecotype Nd-0)

959

960 Section 2B: If you have a metagenotype phenotype recording ‘an inverse
961 gene-for-gene interaction’ (corresponds to footnote 8 in Table 2)

962 Annotate the pathogen effector with the GO Biological process term ‘effector-mediated
963 modulation of host process by symbiont’ ([GO:0140418](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ontology/term/GO:0140418)) or a descendant. If the GO Molecular
964 Function term is known, then this can also be annotated and linked to the relevant GO effector
965 term via an annotation extension.

966 Appendix 1 – table 6 Annotation Extensions (AE) summary for ‘an inverse gene-for-
967 gene interaction’

AE name	Cardinality	Available terms
compared to control genotype	0, 1	Metagenotype identifier
inverse gene-for-gene phenotype	0, 1	‘compatible interaction, functional pathogen necrotrophic effector present, functional host susceptibility locus present’ ‘compatible interaction, functional pathogen necrotrophic effector present, gain of functional host susceptibility locus’ ‘compatible interaction, gain of functional pathogen necrotrophic effector, functional host susceptibility locus present’

		<p>'incompatible interaction, functional pathogen necrotrophic effector present, functional host susceptibility locus absent'</p> <p>'incompatible interaction, functional pathogen necrotrophic effector absent, functional host susceptibility locus present'</p> <p>'incompatible interaction, functional pathogen necrotrophic effector present, functional host susceptibility locus compromised'</p> <p>'incompatible interaction, compromised functional pathogen necrotrophic effector, functional host susceptibility locus present'</p> <p>'incompatible interaction, gain of functional pathogen necrotrophic effector, functional host susceptibility locus compromised'</p> <p>'metagenotype outcome overcome by external condition'</p>
host tissue affected	0, <i>n</i>	BRENDA Tissue Ontology term

968 Example publication: The cysteine rich necrotrophic effector SnTox1 produced by *Stagonospora*
 969 *nodorum* triggers susceptibility of wheat lines harboring Snn1. ([PMID:22241993](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22241993/)).

970 Appendix 1 – figure 11 Gene Ontology (GO) biological process annotation for ‘a
 971 pathogen necrotrophic effector’ within ‘an inverse gene-for-gene interaction’

Species	Gene	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code
<i>P. nodorum</i>	Tox1	GO:0080185	effector-mediated induction of plant hypersensitive response by symbiont	EXP

972

973 Appendix 1 – figure 12 Gene Ontology (GO) molecular function annotation for ‘a
 974 pathogen necrotrophic effector’ within ‘an inverse gene-for-gene interaction’

Species	Gene	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Annotation extension
<i>P. nodorum</i>	Tox1	GO:0140295	pathogen-derived receptor ligand activity	EXP	has_input Snn1 , part_of effector-mediated induction of plant hypersensitive response by symbiont

975

976 Appendix 1 – figure 13 Gene-for-gene phenotype annotations for ‘an inverse gene-for-
 977 gene interaction’

978 Control metagenotypes

979 *Compatible control*

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
Tox1+[WT level] <i>P. nodorum</i> (SN15)	Snn1+[WT level] <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Chinese Spring)	PHIPO:0000480	presence of pathogen-associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	delivery mechanism: culture infiltration	Figure 1	infects_tissue leaf , inverse_gene_for_gene compatible interaction, functional pathogen necrotrophic effector present, functional host susceptibility locus present

980

981 *Incompatible control*

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
Tox1-(no endogenous copy)[Not assayed] <i>P. nodorum</i> (Sn79-1087)	Snn1+[WT level] <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Chinese Spring)	PHIPO:0000481	absence of pathogen-associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	delivery mechanism: pathogen spore inoculation	Figure 5b	infects_tissue leaf , inverse_gene_for_gene incompatible interaction, functional pathogen necrotrophic effector absent, functional host susceptibility locus present

982

983 Altered metagenotypes

984 *Shift from compatible to incompatible interaction*

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
Tox1+[WT level] <i>P. nodorum</i> (SN15)	Snn1- ems237(unknown)[Not assayed] <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Chinese Spring)	PHIPO:0000481	absence of pathogen- associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	delivery mechanism: culture infiltration	Figure 1	infects_tissue leaf , compared_to_control Tox1+[WT level] Parastagonospora nodorum (SN15) / Snn1+[WT level] Triticum aestivum (Chinese Spring) , inverse_gene_for_gene incompatible interaction, functional pathogen necrotrophic effector present, functional host susceptibility locus compromised

985

986 *Shift from incompatible to compatible interaction*

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
+Sn15Tox1A1(transformant, no endogenous copy)[Not assayed] <i>P. nodorum</i> (Sn79-1087)	Snn1+[WT level] <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Chinese Spring)	PHIPO:0000480	presence of pathogen- associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	delivery mechanism: pathogen spore inoculation	Figure 5b	infects_tissue leaf , compared_to_control Tox1-(no endogenous copy)[Not assayed] Parastagonospora nodorum (Sn79-1087) / Snn1+[WT level] Triticum aestivum (Chinese Spring) , inverse_gene_for_gene compatible interaction, gain of functional pathogen necrotrophic effector, functional host susceptibility locus present

987

988 *No shift compared to control, still an incompatible interaction, despite alteration to both*
989 *pathogen and host genotypes*

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
+Sn15Tox1A1(transformant, no endogenous copy)[Not assayed] <i>P. nodorum</i> (Sn79-1087)	Snn1- ems237(unknown)[Not assayed] <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Chinese Spring)	PHIPO:0000481	absence of pathogen- associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	delivery mechanism: pathogen spore inoculation	Figure 5b	infects_tissue leaf , compared_to_control Tox1-(no endogenous copy)[Not assayed] Parastagonospora nodorum (Sn79-1087) / Snn1+[WT level] Triticum aestivum (Chinese Spring) , inverse_gene_for_gene incompatible interaction, gain of functional pathogen necrotrophic effector, functional host susceptibility locus compromised

990

991 Note: the AEs capture the detail of what has occurred within the pathogen-host interactions.

992

994 SECTION 3: Annotation Extensions for curating single species
 995 phenotypes (pathogen phenotypes or host phenotypes)

996 Appendix 1 – table 7 Annotation Extensions (AE) summary for ‘curating single species
 997 phenotypes’

AE name	Cardinality	Available terms
affected proteins	2	UniProtKB accession number
assayed RNA	0, 1	UniProtKB accession number
assayed protein	0, 1	UniProtKB accession number
penetrance	0, 1	qualitative terms ('high', 'medium', 'low', or 'complete') or a quantitative value (a percentage)
severity	0, 1	'high', 'medium', 'low', 'variable severity'
observed in organ	0, 1	BRENDA Tissue Ontology term

998 Section 3A: Example of an in vitro pathogen phenotype (corresponds to
 999 footnote 3 in Table 2)

1000 Example publication: A conserved fungal glycosyltransferase facilitates pathogenesis of plants
 1001 by enabling hyphal growth on solid surfaces. ([PMID:29020037](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29020037/))

1002 A training video is available for the curation of this publication at
 1003 <https://youtu.be/44XGoi6ljgk?t=1738>

1004 Appendix 1 – figure 14 Pathogen phenotype

Species (strain)	Genes	Genotype (allele and expression)	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure
<i>Z. tritici</i> (IPO323)	GT2	ΔGT2-19(deletion)	PHIPO:0001212	decreased hyphal growth	Cell growth assay	water medium, agar plates	Figure 2E

1005

1006 Please note that in this curation example, no AEs were required.

1007 Section 3B: Example of an in vitro pathogen chemistry phenotype
 1008 (corresponds to footnote 9 in Table 2)

1009 Example publication: The T788G mutation in the *cyp51C* gene confers voriconazole resistance
 1010 in *Aspergillus flavus* causing aspergillosis. ([PMID:22314539](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22314539/))

1011 **Appendix 2. Worked example of a curation session.**

1012 This document provides a worked example of the curation process in PHI-Canto for the
1013 publication by King et al. (2017), *A conserved fungal glycosyltransferase facilitates*
1014 *pathogenesis of plants by enabling hyphal growth on solid surfaces* ([PMID:29020037](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29020037/)).

1015 The research study confirms the hypothesis that the GT2 gene is required for the fungal
1016 pathogens *Zymoseptoria tritici* and *Fusarium graminearum* to cause disease on wheat (*Triticum*
1017 *aestivum*). The curation session in PHI-Canto captures this conclusion by annotating a
1018 pathogen–host interaction between *Z. tritici* and *T. aestivum* to show that deletion of the GT2
1019 gene causes loss of pathogenicity in the pathogen, and an absence of pathogen-associated
1020 lesions in the host. The wild type interaction between *Z. tritici* and *T. aestivum* is annotated to
1021 indicate the presence of disease (and lesions), and a corresponding pathogen–host interaction
1022 between *F. graminearum* and *T. aestivum* is annotated to show that deleting GT2 again causes
1023 a loss of pathogenicity and the absence of pathogen-associated lesions in the host.

1024 The example starts with the entry of the publication into PHI-Canto (<https://canto.phi-base.org/>)
1025 and ends with the submission of the curation session for review by curators at PHI-base. The
1026 information curated from this publication is available on the new gene centric PHI-base 5
1027 website (<http://phi5.phi-base.org>, search for PHIG:308 and PHIG:307).

1028 **Entering the publication**

1029 The PHI-Canto homepage provides a text field where publications can be entered by providing
1030 their PubMed ID (PMID). The PMID in this case is 29020037.

1031 **Appendix 2 figure 1**

The image shows a rectangular box with a thin black border. At the top left, the text "Start curating using a PubMed ID:" is displayed in a blue font. Below this text is a white input field containing the text "PMID:29020037". To the right of the input field is a blue button with the word "Find" written in white text.

1032
1033 PHI-Canto will automatically retrieve details of the publication from PubMed so that the curator
1034 can confirm that they have entered the correct PMID.

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1044 **Appendix 2 figure 2**

Publication details	
ID	PMID:29020037
Title	A conserved fungal glycosyltransferase facilitates pathogenesis of plants by enabling hyphal growth on solid surfaces.
Authors	King R, Urban M, Lauder RP, Hawkins N, Evans M, Plummer A, Halsey K, Lovegrove A, Hammond-Kosack K, Rudd JJ
Abstract	Pathogenic fungi must extend filamentous hyphae across solid surfaces to cause diseases of plants. However, the full inventory of genes which support this is incomplete and many may be currently concealed due to their essentiality for the hyphal growth form. During a random T-DNA mutagenesis screen performed on the pleomorphic wheat (<i>Triticum aestivum</i>) pathogen <i>Zymoseptoria tritici</i> , we acquired a mutant unable to extend hyphae specifically when on solid surfaces. In contrast "yeast-like"

1045

1046 After accepting the publication, the curator is prompted for their name, email address, and
1047 (optionally) an ORCID ID, which are used to attribute the curation to the curator, and to contact
1048 the curator in case of problems with the curation session.

1049 **Appendix 2 figure 3**

Curator details	
Before you start curating, please confirm your name and email address:	
Name	<input type="text" value="Martin Urban"/>
Email	<input type="text" value="martin.urban@rothamsted.ac.uk"/>
Your ORCID (optional but recommended):	
	<input type="text" value="0000-0003-2440-4352"/>
Why we collect ORCIDs	

1050

1051 **Specifying genes and species**

1052 The gene is the most basic unit of annotation in PHI-Canto: every other biological feature that
1053 can be annotated involves a gene, so genes are entered first. PHI-Canto uses accession
1054 numbers from the UniProt Knowledgebase (UniProtKB) to uniquely identify proteins for the
1055 genes of interest in the curated publication.

1056 The UniProtKB accession numbers for the publication are shown below.

1057

1058 **Appendix 2 figure 4**

Create gene list for PMID:29020037

Please list the genes studied in this paper using the UniProt identifier (eg. Q00909) separated by commas, spaces, tabs or one per line.
If you have large datasets please consider our [bulk annotation formats](#).
Note: Only supply high confidence interactions for large datasets.
You can edit this list later if you need to add more genes or remove "unused" genes.

1059

1060 Since this publication describes a wild type host species (*T. aestivum*) with no specified genes
1061 of interest, the curator must add the host to the session by entering its NCBI Taxonomy ID in a
1062 separate field.

1063 **Appendix 2 figure 5**

Add host organisms (where the paper has a host with no specified genes):

NCBI Taxon Id	Species	Common name (where available)	
4565	Triticum aestivum	bread wheat	X

1064

1065 PHI-Canto automatically retrieves details of the proteins from UniProtKB, including the gene
1066 name, gene product, and taxonomy (e.g., the species name).

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Appendix 2 figure 6

Pathogen genes

Organism	Gene			
	ID	Name	Product	
<i>Fusarium graminearum</i>	I1RB03	GT2	Type 2 glycosyltransferase	X
<input type="text" value="Type a strain name"/>	<input type="button" value="Add strain"/>	<input type="button" value="Unknown strain"/>		
<i>Zymoseptoria tritici</i>	F9WWD1	GT2	Type 2 glycosyltransferase	X
<input type="text" value="Type a strain name"/>	<input type="button" value="Add strain"/>	<input type="button" value="Unknown strain"/>		

Host genes

Organism	Gene			
	ID	Name	Product	
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	(No genes for this organism)			X
<input type="text" value="Type a strain name"/>	<input type="button" value="Add strain"/>	<input type="button" value="Unknown strain"/>		

1081

1082 **Specifying strains**

1083 The curator must enter the strains for each organism studied in the publication or must specify
1084 when the strain was not known (or not specified in the publication). PHI-Canto provides a pre-
1085 populated list of strains for many species that the curator can select from, though they also have
1086 the option to specify a strain not in the list as free text.

1087 In this publication, the pathogen strains are PH-1 for *F. graminearum* and IPO323 for *Z. tritici*.
1088 Two cultivars of *T. aestivum* were used: cv. Bobwhite and cv. Riband.

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1097 **Appendix 2 figure 7**

Pathogen genes

Organism	Gene			
	ID	Name	Product	
<i>Fusarium graminearum</i>	I1RB03	GT2	Type 2 glycosyltransferase	X
PH-1 X <input type="text" value="Type a strain name"/> <input type="button" value="Add strain"/> <input type="button" value="Unknown strain"/>				
<i>Zymoseptoria tritici</i>	F9WWD1	GT2	Type 2 glycosyltransferase	X
IPO323 X <input type="text" value="Type a strain name"/> <input type="button" value="Add strain"/> <input type="button" value="Unknown strain"/>				

Host genes

Organism	Gene			
	ID	Name	Product	
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	(No genes for this organism)			X
cv. Bobwhite X cv. Riband X <input type="text" value="Type a strain name"/> <input type="button" value="Add strain"/> <input type="button" value="Unknown strain"/>				

1098

1099 Creating alleles and genotypes

1100 In order to show that deleting GT2 in the pathogen causes a loss of pathogenicity, the curator
 1101 must annotate the interaction between the mutant pathogen and its host with a phenotype,
 1102 meaning the interaction must be added to the curation session. In PHI-Canto, interactions are
 1103 represented as *metagenotypes*, which are the combined genotypes of the pathogen and host
 1104 species.

1105 Before the curator can create a metagenotype, they must first create a genotype. Genotypes
 1106 are composed from alleles (except in the case of wild type host genotypes with no specified
 1107 genes, as described later), and metagenotypes are composed from genotypes. So, the curator
 1108 must first create an allele from a gene, then a genotype from an allele, then a metagenotype
 1109 from two genotypes.

1110 The curator starts from the Pathogen genotype management page, following a link from the
 1111 Curation summary page.

1112

1113

1114 **Appendix 2 figure 8**

1115

1116 The curator then selects a pathogen species (*Z. tritici*) from a drop-down menu.

1117 **Appendix 2 figure 9**

1118

1119 Selecting a pathogen species shows a list of genes for the species, with buttons to create types
1120 of alleles. Here, the curator selects 'Deletion' for a deletion allele.

1121 **Appendix 2 figure 10**

1122

1123 The curator is prompted for the strain the deletion occurred in.

1124

1125

1126

1127 **Appendix 2 figure 11**

1128

1129 After selecting this, PHI-Canto creates a genotype containing a single allele, with the allele
1130 name automatically generated from the gene name followed by a delta symbol.

1131 **Appendix 2 figure 12**

1132

1133 The curator will also need to prepare a wild type genotype for the pathogen GT2 gene, which
1134 can be added to the control metagenotype so that any changes in the phenotype (between the
1135 wild type pathogen and the altered pathogen inoculated onto the host) can be properly
1136 annotated. This first requires making a wild type allele for GT2, using the 'Wild type' allele type.

1137 **Appendix 2 figure 13**

Add, view and edit genotypes

Pathogen

Zymoseptoria tritici

Gene Actions

GT2 Deletion Wild type Other genotype

1138

1139 Wild type alleles require the gene expression level to be specified. In this case, there was no
 1140 change in expression level, so the curator selects 'Wild type product level'. PHI-Canto
 1141 automatically creates an allele name by appending a plus symbol to the gene name.

1142 **Appendix 2 figure 14**

Adding allele for GT2

Allele name GT2+

Strain used IPO323

Expression ? Overexpression
 Wild type product level
 Knockdown
 Not assayed

Cancel OK

1143

1144 As genotypes are created, they are added to a table of genotypes on their respective genotype
 1145 management page (Pathogen genotype management for pathogens, Host genotype
 1146 management for hosts).

1147 **Appendix 2 figure 15**

Single-locus genotypes (Mouse over genotypes for actions)

	Alleles	Strain	Annotations	
<input type="checkbox"/>	GT2Δ	IPO323	0	▶
<input type="checkbox"/>	GT2+[WT level]	IPO323	0	▶

Actions:

1148

1149 The curator can repeat the process above to create pathogen genotypes for *F. graminearum*.

1150

1151

1152

1153

1154

1155 **Appendix 2 figure 16**

Single-locus genotypes (Mouse over genotypes for actions)

	Alleles	Strain	Annotations	
<input type="checkbox"/>	GT2Δ	PH-1	0	▶
<input type="checkbox"/>	GT2+[WT level]	PH-1	0	▶

Actions:

1156

1157 Creating metagenotypes for pathogen–host interactions

1158 Metagenotypes are created using the Metagenotype management page, where genotypes
 1159 previously added to the curation session can be combined into a metagenotype. The curator
 1160 can reach this page from the Curation Summary page, or from either the pathogen or host
 1161 genotype management page.

1162 **Appendix 2 figure 17**

1163

1164 The curator starts by selecting a pathogen species from a drop-down menu.

1165 **Appendix 2 figure 18**

1166

1167 Then the curator selects a genotype from the table of pathogen genotypes.

1168

1169

1170

1171

1172

1173 **Appendix 2 figure 19**

1174

1175 Then the curator selects a host genotype. For wild type hosts, PHI-Canto provides a shortcut
1176 where a strain can be selected without needing to create an allele as part of the genotype.

1177 **Appendix 2 figure 20**

1178
1179 The curator selects 'Make metagenotype' to create the metagenotype for the interaction.

1180 **Appendix 2 figure 21**

1181
1182 The metagenotype is displayed in a table as a combination of pathogen and host genotype.

1183

1184

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1190 **Appendix 2 figure 22**

Metagenotypes

Pathogen		Host		
Species (strain)	Genotype	Species (strain)	Genotype	Annotations
Z. tritici (IPO323)	GT2Δ	T. aestivum (cv. Riband)	wild type	0

1191

1192 This process can be repeated to create the metagenotype for the wild type interaction between
1193 *Z. tritici* and *T. aestivum*. In this case, the pathogen genotype containing the wild type GT2 is
1194 selected instead of the deletion allele.

1195 Appendix 2 figure 23

Pathogen

Zymoseptoria tritici

Single locus genotypes

	Genes	Alleles	Strain
<input type="radio"/>	GT2	GT2Δ	IPO323
<input checked="" type="radio"/>	GT2	GT2+[WT level]	IPO323

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1208 **Appendix 2 figure 24**

Pathogen		Host		
Species (strain)	Genotype	Species (strain)	Genotype	Annotations
Z. tritici (IPO323)	GT2Δ	T. aestivum (cv. Riband)	wild type	0
Z. tritici (IPO323)	GT2+[WT level]	T. aestivum (cv. Riband)	wild type	0

1209

1210 Creating the corresponding metagenotypes for *F. graminearum* and *T. aestivum* simply requires
1211 changing the pathogen species and selecting cv. Bobwhite for the host strain.

1212 **Appendix 2 figure 25**

Pathogen		Host		
Species (strain)	Genotype	Species (strain)	Genotype	Annotations
F. graminearum (PH-1)	GT2Δ	T. aestivum (cv. Bobwhite)	wild type	0
F. graminearum (PH-1)	GT2+[WT level]	T. aestivum (cv. Bobwhite)	wild type	0

1213

1214 **Annotating pathogen–host interactions with phenotypes**

1215 Metagenotypes can be annotated with phenotypes by selecting the ‘Annotate pathogen-host
1216 interaction phenotype’ action.

1217

1218

1219 **Appendix 2 figure 26**

Metagenotypes				
Pathogen		Host		Annotations
Species (strain)	Genotype	Species (strain)	Genotype	
Z. tritici (IPO323)	GT2Δ	T. aestivum (cv. Riband)	wild type	0

[Annotate pathogen-host interaction phenotype](#)
[Annotate gene-for-gene phenotype](#)
[Annotate disease name](#)
[View phenotype annotations](#)
[Delete](#)

1220

1221 **Phenotype and evidence**

1222 The first step is to select a term from a controlled vocabulary that describes the phenotype of
1223 the interaction. PHI-Canto uses terms from the Pathogen–Host Interaction Phenotype Ontology
1224 (PHIPO) for this purpose. The primary observed phenotype in this case is the *absence of*
1225 *pathogen-associated host lesions* (PHIPO:0000481).

1226 **Appendix 2 figure 27**

Annotating metagenotype – GT2delta Zymoseptoria tritici (IPO323) / wild type Triticum aestivum (cv. Riband)

Search for pathogen-host interaction phenotype term

Annotate normal or abnormal phenotypes of organisms within this pathogen-host interaction (metagenotype). [more...](#)

Start typing a PHI phenotype in the search box (type at least 2 characters). If you do not find the term you are looking for with your initial search, begin with a broad term (pathogen colonization of host phenotype, binding, effector, host lesion) [more...](#)

absence lesions

- absence of pathogen-associated host lesions (PHIPO:0000481)
- presence of pathogen-associated host lesions (PHIPO:0000480)
- decreased extent of pathogen-associated host lesions (PHIPO:0000985)
- increased extent of pathogen-associated host lesions (PHIPO:0000986)
- presence of pathogen-associated host defense induced lesions (PHIPO:0000461)
- absence of pathogen growth within host (PHIPO:0000363)
- absence of pathogen growth on host surface (PHIPO:0000350)

Term name
absence of pathogen-associated host lesions

Definition
A phenotype where the process of host tissue cell death causing a host lesion is absent.

1227

1228 Upon selecting the term, the curator is shown a description of the term and its synonyms to help
1229 confirm that their chosen term is appropriate.

1230 **Appendix 2 figure 28**

Annotating metagenotype – GT2delta *Zymoseptoria tritici* (IPO323) / wild type *Triticum aestivum* (cv. Riband)

Please read the term definition to ensure that it accurately describes your metagenotype

ID	PHIPO:0000481
Ontology	pathogen_host_interaction_phenotype
Term name	absence of pathogen-associated host lesions
Definition	A phenotype where the process of host tissue cell death causing a host lesion is absent.
Comment	The lesion can be induced by either the pathogen directly killing host tissue (e.g. cell wall degradation), or the host activating its own cell death pathways in defense. Note that if you are curating a necrotroph you need to annotate to PHIPO:0000465.
Synonyms	

Can you use a more specific available term?

- [absence of host-defense induced lesion by host hypersensitive response →](#)
- [absence of pathogen necrotrophic effector-mediated host programmed cell death →](#)

If you need a more specific term to describe the experiment you are annotating, and if none of terms above is appropriate, you can suggest a new term:

[Suggest a new child term for PHIPO:0000481](#)

1231

1232 The curator must select an evidence code for the observation of the phenotype. In this case, the

1233 phenotype was observed macroscopically, and measured qualitatively.

1234 **Appendix 2 figure 29**

1235

1236 The curator may also specify experimental conditions for the experiment – such as the growth

1237 medium, or days elapsed after inoculation of the host. This annotation specifies that the assay

1238 was performed 14 days after inoculation with the *Z. tritici* GT2 deletion mutant.

1239

1240

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1242

1243 **Appendix 2 figure 30**

1244

1245 **Annotation extensions**

1246 PHI-Canto uses annotation extensions to provide additional information about the conditions
1247 and outcome of the pathogen–host interaction. Of particular note are the host tissue infected,
1248 the changes to the infective ability of the pathogen, the presence (or absence) of disease, and
1249 the interaction used as a control for the interaction involving a mutant pathogen.

1250 **Appendix 2 figure 31**

1251

1252 The host tissue that was infected during the interaction is annotated with the 'host tissue
1253 infected' annotation extension. This extension uses ontology terms from the BRENDA Tissue
1254 Ontology (BTO). In this case, the *leaf* (BTO:0000713) of *T. aestivum*
1255 was infected.

1256 **Appendix 2 figure 32**

1257

1258 Changes in the infective ability of the pathogen are annotated with the 'extent of infectivity'
 1259 annotation extension. This extension uses a subset of ontology terms from PHIPO. In this case,
 1260 the curator specifies that the interaction resulted in a *loss of pathogenicity* (PHIPO:0000010).

1261 **Appendix 2 figure 33**

1262

1263 The control interaction (to which the interaction being annotated should be compared) can be
 1264 annotated with the 'compared to control genotype' annotation extension. This annotation allows
 1265 any metagenotype in the curation session to be designated as a control. In this case, the curator
 1266 selects the wild type metagenotype that was created earlier.

1267 **Appendix 2 figure 34**

1268

1269 The presence or absence of disease resulting from the interaction can be annotated with the
1270 'outcome of interaction' annotation extension. This extension uses a subset of ontology terms
1271 from PHIPO. In this case, the curator specifies that no disease was observed as a result of the
1272 interaction: *disease absent* (PHIPO:0001199).

1273

1274

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1278

1279 **Appendix 2 figure 35**

1280

1281 **Figure numbers and comments**

1282 After adding annotation extensions, the curator has the option to provide the figure number from
1283 the publication (if any) that illustrates the phenotype. In this case, the figure was Figure 2E.

1284 **Appendix 2 figure 36**

1285

1286 The curator can also provide additional information in a comments field, in case of details that
1287 are not appropriate for any other field.

1288 Once the above steps are completed, the phenotype annotation is created.

1289 **Appendix 2 figure 37**

Pathogen-host Interaction phenotype							
Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
GT2Δ <i>Z. tritici</i> (IPO323)	wild type <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Riband)	PHIPO:0000481	absence of pathogen-associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	14 days post inoculation	Figure 2E	infects_tissue leaf , infective_ability loss of pathogenicity , compared_to_control GT2+[WT level] <i>Zymoseptoria tritici</i> (IPO323) / wild type <i>Triticum aestivum</i> (cv. Riband) , interaction_outcome disease absent

1290

1291 Copying annotations

1292 The above annotation can be used as a template for the interaction between the wild type
 1293 pathogen and host, since many of the variables are the same. PHI-Canto provides a 'Copy and
 1294 edit' feature that allows curators to use one annotation as a template for creating another.

1295

1296

1297 Appendix 2 figure 38

Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension	
14 days post inoculation	Figure 2E	infects_tissue leaf , infective_ability loss of pathogenicity , compared_to_control GT2+[WT level]	View metagenotype Edit Copy and edit Delete

1298

1299 For the wild type interaction, the pathogen genotype is changed to wild type GT2, the phenotype
 1300 term is changed to *presence of pathogen-associated host lesions* (PHIPO:0000480), the
 1301 interaction outcome is changed to *disease present* (PHIPO:0001200), and the extensions for
 1302 infective ability and control metagenotypes are removed, since they are not applicable.

1303 Appendix 2 figure 39

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
GT2+[WT level] <i>Z. tritici</i> (IPO323)	wild type <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Riband)	PHIPO:0000480	presence of pathogen-associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	14 days post inoculation	Figure 2E	infects_tissue leaf , interaction_outcome disease present

1304

1305 The interaction between *Z. tritici* and *T. aestivum* can also be used as a template for the
 1306 interaction between *F. graminearum* and *T. aestivum*. Here, the pathogen genotype is changed

1307 to the GT2 deletion *F. graminearum*, the host strain is changed to cv. Bobwhite, the
 1308 experimental condition is changed to '13 days post inoculation', the host tissue infected is
 1309 changed to *inflorescence* (BTO:0000628), the control metagenotype is updated accordingly,
 1310 and the figure number is changed to 4E.

1311 **Appendix 2 figure 40**

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID ↕	Term name ↕	Evidence code ↕	Conditions	Figure ↕	Annotation extension ↕
GT2Δ <i>F. graminearum</i> (PH-1)	wild type <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Bobwhite)	PHIPO:0000481	absence of pathogen-associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	13 days post inoculation	Figure 4E	infects_tissue inflorescence , Infective_ability loss of pathogenicity , compared_to_control GT2+[WT level] <i>Fusarium graminearum</i> (PH-1) / wild type <i>Triticum aestivum</i> (cv. Bobwhite) , interaction_outcome disease absent

1312
 1313 The changes required for the wild type interaction between *F. graminearum* and *T. aestivum* are
 1314 the same as those required for *Z. tritici* and *T. aestivum*, since the interaction outcome is the
 1315 same (presence of pathogen-associated host lesions, and presence of disease).

1316

1317

1318

1319 **Appendix 2 figure 41**

Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID ↕	Term name ↕	Evidence code ↕	Conditions	Figure ↕	Annotation extension ↕
GT2+[WT level] <i>F. graminearum</i> (PH-1)	wild type <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Bobwhite)	PHIPO:0000480	presence of pathogen-associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	13 days post inoculation	Figure 4E	infects_tissue leaf , interaction_outcome disease present

1320
 1321 Shown below is a table of all the pathogen–host interaction phenotypes from this curation
 1322 example.

1323 **Appendix 2 figure 42**

Pathogen-host Interaction phenotype							
Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Conditions	Figure	Annotation extension
GT2Δ <i>Z. tritici</i> (IPO323)	wild type <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Riband)	PHIPO:0000481	absence of pathogen-associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	14 days post inoculation	Figure 2E	Infected tissue leaf , Infective ability loss of pathogenicity , compared to control GT2+[WT level] <i>Zyoseptoria tritici</i> (IPO323) / wild type <i>Triticum aestivum</i> (cv. Riband) , Interaction outcome disease absent
GT2+[WT level] <i>Z. tritici</i> (IPO323)	wild type <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Riband)	PHIPO:0000480	presence of pathogen-associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	14 days post inoculation	Figure 2E	Infected tissue leaf , Interaction outcome disease present
GT2Δ <i>F. graminearum</i> (PH-1)	wild type <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Bobwhite)	PHIPO:0000481	absence of pathogen-associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	13 days post inoculation	Figure 4E	Infected tissue inflorescence , Infective ability loss of pathogenicity , compared to control GT2+[WT level] <i>Fusarium graminearum</i> (PH-1) / wild type <i>Triticum aestivum</i> (cv. Bobwhite) , Interaction outcome disease absent
GT2+[WT level] <i>F. graminearum</i> (PH-1)	wild type <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Bobwhite)	PHIPO:0000480	presence of pathogen-associated host lesions	Macroscopic observation (qualitative observation)	13 days post inoculation	Figure 4E	Infected tissue leaf , Interaction outcome disease present

1324

1325 Disease annotation

1326 PHI-Canto provides the ‘Disease name’ annotation type, which is used to annotate a disease to
 1327 a pathogen–host interaction. These annotations highlight the fact that two different pathogens
 1328 infecting different tissue types of the same host have been used in experiments within this
 1329 publication.

1330 Disease name annotations are made on the Metagenotype Management page, via the
 1331 ‘Annotate disease name’ link.

1332

1333

1334 **Appendix 2 figure 43**

Metagenotypes

Pathogen		Host		Annotations
Species (strain)	Genotype	Species (strain)	Genotype	
Z. tritici (IPO323)	GT2+[WT level]	T. aestivum (cv. Riband)	wild type	1

[Annotate pathogen-host interaction phenotype](#)
[Annotate gene-for-gene phenotype](#)
[Annotate disease name](#)
[View phenotype annotations](#)
[Delete](#)

1335

1336 The curator can select a disease from a list of disease names provided by the PHI-base
1337 Disease List (PHIDO). For *Z. tritici*, the disease is *septoria leaf blotch* (PHIDO:0000329).

1338 **Appendix 2 figure 44**

septoria|

- septoria leaf blotch (PHIDO:0000329)
- septoria nodorum blotch (PHIDO:0000330)
- septoria tritici blotch (PHIDO:0000331)

Term name
septoria leaf blotch

Definition
[no definition]

1339

1340 Disease name annotations also allow the host tissue infected to be specified. In this case, the
1341 tissue is the *leaf* (BTO:0000713).

1342 **Appendix 2 figure 45**

host tissue infected

leaf

- leaf (BTO:0000713)
- leaf tip (BTO:0001814)
- leaf bud (BTO:0003668)
- leaf axil (BTO:0000714)
- leaf base (BTO:0000715)
- flag leaf (BTO:0002811)
- true leaf (BTO:0003141)
- leaf disc (BTO:0003938)

Term name
leaf

Definition
A lateral outgrowth from a plant stem that is typically a flattened expanded variably shaped greenish organ, constitutes a unit of the foliage, and functions primarily in food manufacture by photosynthesis.

1343

1344 The curator has the option to provide the figure number and additional comments. In this case,
1345 the figure numbers are 1 and 2.

1346 **Appendix 2 figure 46**

Figure or table: Figure 1, 2

1347

1348 Once this step is completed, the disease name annotation is created.

1349

1350 **Appendix 2 figure 47**

Disease name					
Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Figure	Annotation extension
GT2+[WT level] <i>Z. tritici</i> (IPO323)	wild type <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Riband)	PHIDO:0000329	septoria leaf blotch	Figure 1, 2	infects_tissue leaf

1351

1352 The same process can be followed to create the Disease name annotation for *F. graminearum*:
1353 the genotype is the wild type GT2, the host cultivar is *cv. Bobwhite*, the disease is *fusarium ear*
1354 *blight* (PHIDO:0000162), the host tissue infected is the *inflorescence* (BTO:0000628), and the
1355 figure number is 4.

1356 **Appendix 2 figure 48**

Disease name					
Pathogen genotype	Host genotype	Term ID	Term name	Figure	Annotation extension
GT2+[WT level] <i>F. graminearum</i> (PH-1)	wild type <i>T. aestivum</i> (cv. Bobwhite)	PHIDO:0000162	fusarium ear blight	Figure 4	infects_tissue inflorescence

1357

1358 **Gene Ontology annotation**

1359 PHI-Canto also provides the ability to annotate biological processes, molecular functions, and
1360 cellular components associated with wild type versions of genes, using terms from the Gene
1361 Ontology (GO). In this publication, GT2 is described as having glycotransferase activity as its
1362 molecular function, so the curator can annotate this.

1363 Gene Ontology annotations are made by selecting the gene from the Curation Summary page.

1364 **Appendix 2 figure 49**

Annotate genes ?

Pathogens

Fusarium graminearum

[GT2](#)

Zymoseptoria tritici

[GT2](#)

1365

1366 The gene details page has a list of available annotation types.

1367

1368 **Appendix 2 figure 50**

Choose curation type for GT2: ?

- [GO molecular function](#) ?
- [GO biological process](#) ?
- [GO cellular component](#) ?
- [Protein modification](#) ?
- [Physical interaction](#) ?
- [Wild-type RNA level](#) ?
- [Wild-type protein level](#) ?
- [Single allele phenotype](#) ?

1369

1370 The curator selects the GO Molecular Function annotation type and is prompted for a term from
 1371 the Gene Ontology. In this case, the correct term is *glycotransferase activity* (GO:0016757).

1372 **Appendix 2 figure 51**

glycosyltransferase

glycosyltransferase activity (GO:0016757)	<p>Term name glycosyltransferase activity</p> <p>Definition Catalysis of the transfer of a glycosyl group from one compound (donor) to another (acceptor).</p>
UDP-glycosyltransferase activity (GO:0008194)	
phenanthrol glycosyltransferase activity (GO:0019112)	
peptidoglycan glycosyltransferase activity (GO:0008955)	
transfer ribonucleate glycosyltransferase activity (GO:0008479) (synonym)	
kinetin UDP glycosyltransferase activity (GO:0102694)	

1373

1374 The curator must provide an evidence code from a controlled list specified by the Gene
1375 Ontology. The appropriate evidence code in this case is a *Traceable Author Statement* in the
1376 publication.

1377

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1386 **Appendix 2 figure 52**

1387

1388 There are many annotation extensions available for GO annotations, but in this case, none of
1389 them are applicable (or required), so the curator skips this step.

1390 **Appendix 2 figure 53**

Annotation extensions

These extension types are available for *glycosyltransferase activity* (GO:0016757):

with host species
has function during
physical location
involved in biological process
PR:nnn ID for gene product form
qualifier

1391

1392 Figure numbers can be specified for GO annotations: in this case, the relevant figure is Figure
1393 3.

1394 **Appendix 2 figure 54**

Figure or table:

1395

1396 Once this step is completed, the molecular function annotation is created.

1397

1398

1399 **Appendix 2 figure 55**

GO molecular function

Species	Gene	Term ID	Term name	Evidence code	Figure
<i>Z. tritici</i>	GT2	GO:0016757	glycosyltransferase activity	TAS	Figure 3

1400

Other annotation types

1402 The publication contains other information which is not included in this worked example for the
1403 sake of brevity. In the real curation session, this other information is captured as the following
1404 annotations:

- 1405 • **GO biological process** annotations indicate that GT2 is involved in the hyphal growth
1406 process.

- 1407 ● **GO cellular component** annotations indicate that GT2 is located in the hyphal cell wall.
- 1408 ● **Pathogen phenotype** annotations capture information about the pathogen *in vitro*,
- 1409 specifically normal and altered phenotypes for unicellular population growth, hyphal
- 1410 growth, cellular melanin accumulation, filament morphology, and so on.

1411 All these annotation types use the same annotation process as the annotation types described
1412 above.

1413 Submitting the curation session

1414 Once the curator has made all their annotations, the curation session is submitted to the PHI-
1415 base team for review.

1416 Appendix 2 figure 56

1417

1418 The curator can use a text box to provide any information that is outside the scope of the
1419 curation process before finishing the submission process. Once the submission process is
1420 finished, the curation session can no longer be edited except by members of the PHI-base
1421 team, who have the option to reactivate the session in case changes are required by the original
1422 curator.

1423 Appendix 3. Author checklist prior to publication.

1424 Here, we have developed a list of important points for an author to consider prior to submitting a
1425 manuscript for publication. Nine key points are displayed in Appendix 3 – table 1.

1426 Appendix 3 - table 1 Author checklist prior to publication.

Point number	Point for author to consider
1	Use the most current gene name. Take care with synonyms. Prefix the gene name with the genus and species initials if the same gene name exists in multiple species.
2	If reporting on a new (gene) sequence, submit your sequence to NCBI GenBank or the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), then obtain an accession number prior to publication. Record this accession number within the manuscript. If reporting on a gene with an existing accession number, make sure this is reported in the manuscript. Please record the UniProtKB accession number for the protein of the gene, where available.

	Provide or use any existing informative allele or line designations for mutations and transgenes.
3	Provide a binomial species name for pathogen and host organisms, not just a common name. If possible, please also include NCBI Taxonomy IDs for the pathogen and host organisms at the rank of species.
4	Describe the tissue or organ in which the experimental observations were made (controlled language can be found in the BRENDA Tissue Ontology, see https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/bto).
5	Describe any experimental techniques used, and accurately record any chemicals or reagents used.
6	When writing an article, try to keep the use of descriptive language as accurate and controlled as possible. For example, do not use 'reduced pathogenicity' or 'loss of virulence', as these terms can be misleading: it would be more accurate to use 'reduced virulence' and 'loss of pathogenicity', respectively. Ideally, try to follow the terminology of an existing ontology: this will make the data easier to extract and reuse. Relevant ontologies include PHIPO and GO (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/phipo , https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/go).
7	Document all the key information for the paper: do not rely on citing past papers for information on the pathogen used, or the strain used, and so on.
8	Think carefully when choosing keywords for your manuscript to ensure that the publication can be located by PHI-base's keyword searches. One example of an ideal keyword is 'pathogen-host interaction'.
9	Record the provenance of the pathogen strain: for example, whether it is a lab strain or a field isolate, or if the strain was obtained from a stock center or as a gift from another lab.

1427

1428 **Supplementary file 1. Mapping display name to**
1429 **relation name for Annotation Extensions in PHI-**
1430 **Canto.**

PHI-Canto display name	Annotation extension relation
compared to control	compared_to_control
gene-for-gene interaction	gene_for_gene_interaction
inverse gene-for-gene interaction	inverse_gene_for_gene_interaction
penetrance	has_penetrance

extent of infectivity	infective_ability
host tissue infected	infects_tissue
outcome of interaction	interaction_outcome
observed in organ	observed_organ
affected proteins (add TWO i.e., both binding partners)	assayed_using
assayed protein	assayed_using
assayed RNA	assayed_using
severity	has_severity

1431

1432 **Supplementary file 2.** PomBase annotation extensions also used in PHI-Canto. – Large Excel
 1433 File please go directly to eLIFE publication

Supplementary file 2. PomBase annotation extensions also used in PHI-Canto.	
Annotation type	Annotation extension name
GO biological process	PR:nnn ID for gene product form
	acetylation of
	exports
	folds
	glycosylation of
	happens during
	involved in degradation of
	localizes
	maintains location of
	occurs at
	phosphorylation of
	processes
	qualifier
	regulates acetylation of
	regulates activity of
	regulates binding between
	regulates catabolism of
	regulates localization of
	regulates modification of
	regulates processing of
regulates targeting of	
regulates transcription of	
regulates transport of	
silences	
stabilizes	
targets	
transports	
GO cellular component	PR:nnn ID for gene product form
	found at genomic region
	observed in this location during (cell cycle phase or stress response) qualifier

1434

	qualifier
	PR:nnn ID for gene product form
	active in
	acts on
	anchors
	binds (PR:nnn ID for bound protein form)
	binds (RNA gene or type)
	binds chromatin region
	binds ligand
	binds region
	chaperone for
	cleaves
	deacetylates
	dephosphorylates
	deubiquitinates
	exchange factor for
	has function during
	has input
GO molecular function	has ligand (protein or chemical substance)
	involved in biological process
	isomerizes
	methyates
	modifies
	palmitoylates
	phosphorylates
	prenylates
	qualifier
	recruits
	regulates activity of
	regulates activity of transcription factor
	regulates transcription of
	sequesters
	transports
	transports (protein or RNA)
	ubiquitinates
	uridylylates
RNA level	during
	in presence of
	in presence of
	absent during
	added by
	added during
	cellular amount of modification fluctuates during
	position modified
Protein Modification	present during
	proportion of proteins with modification
	removed by
	removed during
	required for activity
	required for process

1435

1436

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1439 **Supplementary file 3. PHI-base nine high level**
 1440 **term mapping to PHI-Canto.**

PHI-Canto term name ¹	Definition	Term ID	High level term
Increased resistance to chemical ²	A single species population phenotype in which a population shows increased resistance to a chemical stimulus. ³	PHIPO:0000022 ⁵	Genotype ⁷ with P
Increased sensitivity to chemical ²	A single species population phenotype in which a population shows decreased resistance to a chemical stimulus. ⁴	PHIPO:0000021	Genotype with P
Inviabile population	An organism population phenotype in which no organisms in the population are viable.	PHIPO:0000513	Genotype with P
Loss of pathogenicity	A phenotype where the ability of a pathogen, to produce an infectious disease in another organism is abolished (pathogenicity was present and is now absent).	PHIPO:0000010	Metagenotype ⁸ w
Unaffected pathogenicity	A phenotype where the ability of a pathogen, to produce an infectious disease in another organism is unaffected (i.e., the same as wild type, it could be pathogenic or non-pathogenic).	PHIPO:0000004	Metagenotype w
Reduced virulence	A phenotype where the degree to which a pathogen (species or strain) is able to cause infectious disease in another organism is increased (i.e., more symptoms than normal).	PHIPO:0000015	Metagenotype w
Increased virulence	A phenotype where the degree to which a pathogen (species or strain) is able to cause infectious disease in another organism is increased (i.e., more symptoms than normal).	PHIPO:0000014	Metagenotype w
Loss of mutualism	A phenotype in which the balance of symbiotic mutualism has been disrupted compared to the normal interaction and the endosymbiont organism is able to show greater biomass within the host and/or the formation of visible disease formation symptoms compared to the normal interaction.	PHIPO:0000207	Metagenotype w
Effector-mediated modulation of host process by symbiont	A process mediated by a molecule secreted by a symbiont that results in the modulation (either activation or suppression) of a host structure or process. The host is defined as the larger of the organisms involved in a symbiotic interaction.	GO:0140418 ⁶	Gene ¹⁰ with GO

1441

1442 ¹ Some term names have been updated since initial publication in Urban et al., 2015 NAR (PMID:25414340). Specifically, 'inviabile
 1443 population' was formerly 'lethal' and 'loss of mutualism' was formerly 'enhanced antagonism'.

1444 ² Lower ranked terms, containing specific chemicals names, are mapped up to this term.

1445 ³ Additional definition gloss: Resistance to a chemical is usually measured by determining the maximum concentration of the
 1446 chemical at which a population grows and divides.

1447 ⁴ Additional definition gloss: Resistance to a chemical is usually measured by determining the maximum concentration of the
 1448 chemical at which a population grows and divides. Typically, populations are deemed sensitive to a chemical if they stop growing
 1449 (and may die) at a concentration of the chemical that allows wild type populations to grow.

1450 ⁵ PHIPO is the Pathogen-Host Interaction Phenotype Ontology.

1451 ⁶ GO is the Gene Ontology.

1452 ⁷ A single species genotype can be either a pathogen or a host genotype.

1453 ⁸ A metagenotype consists of both a pathogen genotype and a host genotype in the context of a pathogen-host interaction.

1454 ⁹ AE is an Annotation Extension. Annotation extensions enable additional data to be related to a primary annotation.

1455 ¹⁰ This curation type does not refer to annotating a phenotype to a genotype, but instead refers to annotating a GO term to a gene
 1456 product.

1457 ¹¹ The curator has the option to add a GO Molecular Function term annotation to the pathogen effector, if known.

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1459 **Supplementary File 4** PHI-Canto species and strain lists for pathogens and hosts.

Sheet	Column	Description
Supplementary file 4. PHI-Canto species and strain lists for pathogens and hosts.		
This workbook contains lists of pathogen and host species and strains that are used in PHI-Canto. The species and strains were extracted from data already curated in PHI-base version 4. Note that this list does not constrain the choices of data available to curators, since curators are free to enter an accession from any species in UniProtKB into PHI-Canto, and curators may also enter their own strain names as free text (in the case that the required strain is not recorded in these lists). However, the host species list does constrain which host species may be added with no gene of interest (i.e. as wild type). Note also that strain cross references are currently unused by PHI-Canto, but are included here for completeness.		
Pathogen species	ncbi_taxid	The NCBI Taxonomy identifier of the pathogen species.
	scientific_name	The scientific name of the pathogen species, as it appears in PHI-base.
	common_name	The common name (if any) of the pathogen species, as it appears in PHI-base.
Host species	ncbi_taxid	The NCBI Taxonomy identifier for the host species.
	scientific_name	The scientific name of the host species, as it appears in PHI-base.
	common_name	The common name (if any) of the host species, as it appears in PHI-base.
Pathogen strains	ncbi_taxid	The NCBI Taxonomy identifier of the pathogen species corresponding to the strain.
	scientific_name	The scientific name of the pathogen species corresponding to the strain.
	strain	The primary name of the pathogen strain.
	synonyms	Synonymous names of the primary pathogen strain name, as curated by PHI-base.
	cross_references	Cross-references to identifiers from other biological databases or ontologies. Currently unused for pathogen strains.
Host strains	ncbi_taxid	The NCBI Taxonomy identifier of the host species corresponding to the strain.
	scientific_name	The scientific name of the host species corresponding to the strain.
	strain	The primary name of the host strain.
	synonyms	Synonymous names of the primary host strain name, as curated by PHI-base.
	cross_references	Cross-references to identifiers from other biological databases or ontologies: 'CVCL' for Cellosaurus, 'BTO' for the BRENDA Tissue Ontology, 'WBStrain' for WormBase, and 'MGI' for Mouse Genome Informatics.

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1463 **Supplementary File 5** Mapping between strains in PHI-base and PHI-Canto.

Column	Description
NCBI taxid	The NCBI Taxonomy ID for the organism corresponding to the strain name. Note that PHI-base aggregates strains at the taxonomic rank of species, and this convention is also followed in PHI-Canto.
Scientific name	The scientific name for the organism as it appears in PHI-base.
Nearest taxid	The NCBI Taxonomy ID for the nearest taxonomic rank to the strain: 'nearest' in this sense is anything above the rank of strain. Taxonomic identifiers at the rank of strain are not used because the NCBI Taxonomy is not minting any new identifiers at this rank, but PHI-base have a continued need to curate strains with no entry in the NCBI Taxonomy. Effectively, this column stores the taxonomic rank of the organism corresponding to the strain, prior to the aggregation of taxonomic identifiers at the species level.
Comment	Comments describing potential problems with strain name curation, such as ambiguous naming, misidentified cell lines, and missing cross-references.
Old strain name	The strain name as it appeared in the PHI-Canto strain list or PHI-base database prior to review and amendment.
New strain name	The strain name as it appears after review and amendment, and as it appears in PHI-Canto at the time of this publication. Note that taxonomic information has been removed from all strain names where there is a corresponding NCBI Taxonomy ID that can supply the same information. However, for cases where a taxonomic rank is not found in NCBI Taxonomy (e.g. some serotypes), it is retained in the strain name so that such information is still available for selection by curators. Blank values in this column indicate that the strain has been excluded from PHI-Canto.
Synonyms	Exact synonyms for the strain name in the 'New strain name' column. Note that the designation of a strain as 'primary' does not necessarily imply that it takes precedence over any synonym: the primary name is often chosen based on the value that was originally curated in PHI-base. In cases where an authoritative reference for strain names exists, then the primary name will match that nomenclature, and any synonyms specified by the authority will be included in this column.
Abbreviation	An abbreviation for the strain name, typically derived from existing conventions in the literature. Abbreviations are included only for the sake of convenience: to allow more space-efficient display of long strain names in PHI-Canto.
Cross references	Cross-references from the strain name to systematic identifiers in other biological databases or ontologies that describe the strain. The relation between identifier prefixes and their respective data sources are described below: CVCL: Cellosaurus BTO: BRENDA Tissue Ontology WBStrain: WormBase MGI: Mouse Genome Informatics

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1466 Main Figure supplementals

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Figure 3 – figure supplement 1. Canto entity relationship model.

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Simplified UML class diagram showing the relations between entities (things of interest) in a Canto curation session. The numbers on the connecting lines represent the cardinality of the relation, meaning how many of one entity can be related to another entity: 0..n means 'zero or more'; 1..n means 'one or more'. Lines with a hollow arrowhead indicate that the target entity (at the head of the arrow) is a generalization of the source entity (at the tail of the arrow). Boxes outlined in bold indicate new entities which were added to support curation in PHI-Canto.

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1478 **Figure 3 – figure supplement 2.** Entity–relationship
1479 model for the main Canto database.

1480 This database stores data that is shared across all
1481 curation sessions. Database tables are represented
1482 as boxes, and arrows between boxes indicate a
1483 connection between tables. The table and property
1484 names contain numerous abbreviations, which are
1485 expanded as follows: curs: curation session, pub:
1486 publication, db: database, xref: cross-reference, cv:
1487 controlled vocabulary.

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1490 **Figure 3 – figure supplement 3.** Entity–relationship
 1491 model for a Canto curation session database.

1492 This database stores data that is unique to a
 1493 curation session. Database tables are represented
 1494 as boxes, and arrows between boxes indicate a
 1495 connection between tables. The ‘pub’ table stands
 1496 for ‘publication’.

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1499 **Figure 4 – figure supplement 1. Alternative**
 1500 **curation step workflow.**

1501 The flow diagram represents the PHI-Canto curation process from beginning to end in 5 steps.
 1502 This diagram is an alternative representation to the image depicted in Figure 4. During step 2 of
 1503 the workflow, the curator chooses either the gene annotation or genotype / metagenotype
 1504 annotation process. Multiple annotations can be made using both annotation processes which
 1505 can then be submitted for review.

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1507 **Figure 4 – figure supplement 2. What you need to**
 1508 **curate a publication into PHI-Canto.**

- 1509
- 1510 1. The PubMed ID of the peer-reviewed publication.
 - 1511 2. Your email address, so we can contact you regarding your curation session.
 - 1512 3. UniProtKB accession numbers for the pathogen and host gene products studied within
the publication.
 - 1513 4. The binomial names of the pathogen and host species studied within the publication.
 - 1514 5. Details of the experimental strains used within the publication.

1515 **Figure 4 – figure supplement 3. Instructions on**
1516 **how to look up a UniProtKB ID.**

1517 UniProtKB is divided into two sources: UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot, which contains manually
1518 annotated entries; and UniProtKB/TrEMBL, which contains unreviewed entries that are
1519 automatically annotated by prediction systems. PHI-Canto permits annotations on entries from
1520 either source, although UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot entries are preferred (owing to their higher
1521 quality).

1522 **Finding genes in UniProtKB**

1523 PHI-Canto uses UniProt Knowledgebase (UniProtKB) gene accession numbers to disambiguate
1524 genes/proteins. This is to ensure that we are talking about the correct gene product – especially
1525 as the same names are sometimes used for different proteins – and to standardize entries,
1526 because not all strains are in UniProt.

1527 1. **Identify the reference proteome** (we use the designated reference proteome to
1528 integrate different strain information at the gene level in PHI-base). In PHI-Canto you will
1529 be able to specify the strain you used.

1530 Look up the reference proteome for your organism using the species name
1531 (https://www.uniprot.org/help/reference_proteome).

1532 If there is no reference proteome use the strain studied.

1533 2. **Identify the gene of interest** in the reference proteome:

1534 Start from the UniProt homepage (<https://www.uniprot.org>), then perform any of the
1535 following steps:

1536 Search for the author assigned gene name/primary name (e.g., Tri5) or synonyms, plus species
1537 name (e.g., *Fusarium graminearum*).

1538 OR

1539 If the gene does not have a 'given name' but a locus ID is provided, search using the locus_id
1540 (e.g., FGRRES_03537) plus species name (e.g., *Fusarium graminearum*). If the entry identifier
1541 used is not the reference strain, copy the protein sequence and go to the BLAST step below.

1542 OR

1543 Search on a protein description (e.g., **Trichodiene synthase**)

1544 OR

1545 Obtain the protein sequence for your gene of interest and BLAST against UniprotKB
1546 (<https://www.uniprot.org/blast/>) with your protein sequence.

1547 **Note:** If there are multiple entries for your gene product from the reference strain, please select
1548 the 'Reviewed entry'. Use the left-hand filter for 'Reviewed entries'.

1549 OR

1550 If the gene cannot be located in UniProt, contact the authors, UniProt, or PHI-base for help
 1551 locating the canonical database entry.

1552 3. **Add the entry into PHI-Canto.** Once the entry of interest is located, select the entry
 1553 accession number (also called 'Entry') from column 1 of the results table, and use this to
 1554 retrieve the entry into PHI-Canto on the gene entry page. **Caution:** Do not confuse the
 1555 'Entry' column with the 'Entry name' column. PHI-Canto uses the accession number to
 1556 retrieve details (such as the gene name, gene product, and organism). If PHI-Canto is
 1557 unable to find your entry, check for typos (e.g., 0 for O), ensure you are using the 'entry'
 1558 not 'entry name', and check that your accession is from UniProtKB, not UniParc.

1559 **Figure 5 – figure supplement 1. Resources relied**
 1560 **upon by PHI-Canto.**

Category	Resource	URL	Description of use
Databases	PHI-base	http://www.phi-base.org/	To display Pathogen-Host Interaction annotation data.
	UniProtKB	https://www.uniprot.org/uniprot/	To identify the gene product under annotation.
	NCBI Taxonomy	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy	To identify the species of the organism being annotated.
PHI-base controlled vocabularies	PHIDO	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/PHI-base/phido/master/phido.obo	To annotate wild type metagenotypes with the 'disease caused'.
	Pathogen Host Interactions Experimental Conditions Ontology	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/PHI-base/phi-eco/master/phi-eco.obo	To annotate experimental conditions on phenotype annotations.
OBO ontologies	BioGrid	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/BioGRID/BioGRID-Ontologies/master/BioGRIDExperimentalSystems.obo	To annotate physical interactions.
	BRENDA Tissue Ontology	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/bto.obo	To annotate the extension 'infected tissue'.
	ChEBI ontology	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/chebi.obo	To annotate extensions for Gene Ontology and RNA level annotations.
	Gene Ontology	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/go/go-basic.obo	To annotate gene products.

Pathogen-Host Interactions Phenotype Ontology	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/phipo.obo	To annotate genotypes with the observed pathogen host interaction phenotype.
PSI-Mod Mass Modifications Ontology	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/mod.obo	To annotate protein chemical modifications.
Relations Ontology	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ro.obo	Contains essential relations for OBO ontologies; needed to initialize Canto.
Sequence Ontology	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/so.obo	To annotate extensions for Gene Ontology annotations.

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